

**AUTOMATION OF FASHION SHOW VIDEO PLAYLIST FOR FASHION ONE
INC.**

A Capstone Project
Presented to the Faculty of the
Department of Computer and Information Sciences
University of San Carlos

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
CERTIFICATE IN COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY

By:

KHIM R. COLE
JOMAR Q. EDAÑO
MARIA RAZEL A. INOC
RACQUEL L. ROSEL

JOHN REXTER B. FLORES
Capstone Adviser

May 2019

CERTIFICATE OF AUTHORSHIP/ORIGINALITY

This is to certify that the authors are responsible for the work submitted in this capstone. The intellectual content of this capstone is a product of original work. Any assistance that the authors received in the preparation and work of the capstone itself has been acknowledged. In addition, the authors certify that the materials and literatures taken from other sources are properly quoted.

KHIM R. COLE

JOMAR Q. EDAÑO

MARIA RAZEL A. INOC

RACQUEL L. ROSEL

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

With our deep appreciation and a genuine pleasure to express our sincere and deep sense of thanks to all people who were involved to make this capstone project successful.

The proponents were thankful for each other's hard work and patience just to comply with the documents. Also, with the help of our school adviser, Sir John Rex Paña for his unending reminder, well-disciplined way of guiding and teaching us. To our thesis adviser, John Rexter Flores, who helped us since the beginning of finding the best research and implemented the best solution to solve our chosen research problem. More thanks to spread to our beloved PN family , who never failed to show their support and good vibe cheers. Most specially to Sir Junrey, Sir Rene, Ate Thessa and to all the training team, beloved current and past educators, who also inspired us to do more and thanks to our company mentors.

Of course, to our beloved family who never stopped supporting us mentally, emotionally and socially. For providing us all we need no matter how hard it was on their part but still continuing to cheer us up. Family who inspired us and for making us realize that we were able to step up no matter what and where we are now. To those people that did not realize that they already had been part of this project and had already helped us even in the littlest thing (in terms of technical works or not).

Those help offered really matter and we are very thankful for that. Friends, classmates, USC school personnel, PN family and our respective families, we worked as one. All of you motivated us to work more and to step higher and higher without even realizing that each of us contributed more than enough. Thank you for believing in us!

ABSTRACT

Manually handling tasks is one of the common problems of the company. It is very prone to having a lot of failures most especially when handling equipment rental, as well as post production services for. Fashion One Incorporated is a global Television network broadcasting 24/7 an international fashion and entertainment channel that focuses on beauty, glamour, style and luxury. Currently Fashion One Incorporated's video approach in scheduling their video clips playlist is done manually.

The main goal of this study is to provide an automated fashion video clips playlist for Fashion One Incorporated by using the technologies available: Laravel, Bootstrap, PHP etc. and using the V Model Methodology with the Top-Down Development Approach on Automated Playlist having V Model Methodology as the backbone structure of the entire development. The system will automate the clip duration, select and identify clips from the database based on the client's requirements.

This study can be helpful to the communities and to some individuals. People nowadays are attracted to new and evolving technologies. In some businesses, personal interest, etc., this system will promote and will give a big impact to society and any individuals that will prefer automation rather than manual process which means that in manual, people exert more effort, time, less productivity, and to avoid human failures.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iii
ABSTRACT	iv
TABLE OF CONTENTS	v
LIST OF FIGURES	vi
LIST OF TABLES	vii
CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Rationale of the Study	1
1.2 Statement of the Problem	2
1.2.1 General Objective	2
1.2.2 Specific Objectives	2
1.3 Significance of the Study	2
1.4 Scope and Limitations	3
CHAPTER 2 RELATED SYSTEMS	5
CHAPTER 3 TECHNICAL BACKGROUND	8
CHAPTER 4 DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY	12
4.1 Conceptual Framework	12
4.2 Analysis and Design	13
4.3 Development Model	14
4.4 Development Approach	15
4.5 Software Development Tools	16
4.6 Project Management	16
4.6.1 Schedule and Timeline	17
4.6.2 Responsibilities	18
4.6.3 Budget and Cost Management	19
4.7 Verification, Validation and Testing	19
CHAPTER 5 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS	21
5.1 Systems Capability	21
5.2 Major Modules	21

5.3 Verification	22
5.4 Validation	25
CHAPTER 6 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	28
6.1 Summary	28
6.2 Conclusions	28
6.3 Recommendations	29
GLOSSARY	30
BIBLIOGRAPHY	34

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Conceptual Diagram	12
Figure 2: Entity Relationship Diagram	13
Figure 3: V-Model	14
Figure 4: Top-Down Approach	15
Figure 5: Pie Chart	25
Figure 6: Bar Graph	27

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Comparison Matrix	7
Table 2: Software Development Tools	16
Table 3: 1st Semester 2018	17
Table 4: 2nd Semester 2018 - 2019	18
Table 5: Responsibilities	18
Table 6: Project Budget and Cost in Development Phase	19
Table 7: Test Cases	22
Table 8: Table Summary Formula	25
Table 9: Validation Results of Average Score Interpretation	26

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rationale of the Study

As the proponents searched for a problem that needed a solution, the proponents found out that Fashion One Inc. which was the proponents' client, had a problem in terms of manual validating, generating, calculating video clip duration, and scheduling for the right video clip playlist. In making a fashion video playlist manually, human errors sometimes occur from time to time and that was what they were trying to avoid. With these problems, the proponents conceptualized a web-based system that would automate the video clip playlist in Fashion One Incorporated. The main idea of this system was to look for the right clip at the right place and at the right time, to lessen time and effort, to increase productivity, and to avoid human failures.

According to Sasongko (2011), in developing a video summarisation system, the main motivation in creating an automatic generation of effective video was to manage a large amount of raw video that requires more time and effort. This system helped to resolve "information overload" by emphasizing important information and de-emphasizing or eliminating less important details in videos. The system was useful to improve existing summarisation techniques to focus practicality and user satisfaction. It also helped for a higher rate of user satisfaction and having low computing requirements. The system showed quick visualisation of useful information from both video itself and external sources.

The development of visualisation techniques in presenting videos should suit for automated way from their manual process of creating fashion show video playlists for Fashion One Incorporated was the way to solve the problem to

lessen time, effort, and to avoid human failures. Using this technique, it also lessened the involvement of human interaction with not much pressure as the machine itself could do it automatically.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

1.2.1 General Objective

This study aimed to develop an automated fashion show video clips playlist system in Fashion One Incorporated that would change their previous work from manual to automated process for a faster and reliable result of the project.

1.2.2 Specific Objectives

This study aimed to:

1. Determine and analyze the current process in scheduling the video clips.
2. Design and develop a system for video clip playlist automation.
3. Deploy the system to Fashion One Incorporated using a local host.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This project was a significant endeavor in promoting a good work environment in the workplace and motivations of its employees in making a fashion video playlist manually to look for the right clip at the right place and on the right time, to lessen time, effort and productivity, and to avoid human failures. As already discussed, in the manual process it was very prone that human errors sometimes occur from time to time and that was what they were trying to avoid. To respond to the needs of the employees and managers, our system assured a

competitive advantage. That was to change the manual process to an automated one. This project was beneficial to the following:

Fashion One Incorporated. The system would provide an efficient way in automating the video clips playlist based on the requirements needed for each show. Fashion One Incorporated could not only use the system to have an efficient result of the schedule but also to lessen the time and effort of the employees and increase productivity.

Television Network. Like Fashion One Incorporated, other television network companies could also use the system for their work and projects related to automated scheduling of presentations or shows. They could change their previous work from manual to automated for a faster and more reliable result.

Future Researchers. This study would be useful to the future researchers who also aimed to develop a system that would automate in choosing and creating a video clips playlist in its given schedule. This system could be one of the related systems to the future researchers as this project data and methods would give an idea or information related on how to automate a video clips playlist.

1. 4 Scope and Limitations

This study was conducted to develop a system that provides an efficient and reliable performance output to our client in Fashion One Incorporated. From their manual work of identifying and choosing fashion show video clips playlist based on the show schedule given by the clients.

This study only played specific video clips in a playlist when it passed in a specific terms and conditions. We only covered two countries, Philippines and Russia. The system focused on automating the generation of a fashion show

video playlist based on the given requirements of the client , which was Fashion One Incorporated. The system was limited to identify and to receive data of video clips from client. 1.) The client would only input the schedule of the shows of the specific day and the system would identify and chose a multiple video clips for 13 minutes and 20 to 30 seconds, 1 minute for advertisement and 20 to 30 seconds for fillers that would fit the total durations of 15 minutes for that specific show and would automate the scheduled playlist. 2.) The system could only choose the clips if it was not played for the last 6 hours. 3.) Clips was not added if its PG ratings was prohibited in the selected server. 4.) Clips language should be the same in the server language, if not, clip should be set with the same language of the selected server; anything else would not be covered. This project was an intranet site and only compatible with Google Chrome. This would be deployed using local host as this system could only be used and accessed in Fashion One Incorporated.

CHAPTER 2

RELATED SYSTEMS

According to Laureshyn (2010), Automated Video Analysis to Road User Behaviour was one of the promising tools for traffic behaviour research in processing videos. It enabled a collection of micro-level data for a large scale of users and provided a detailed description for their motion.

According to Kumar (2012), the method of this system was to retrieve and identify the plurality of multimedia content from multimedia database and generate ordered playlist according to the selection responses received from the user. Video based on multimedia playlists might be generated. And thus, it might be updated with one or more advertisements. Automated Playlist Generation System, like the other related systems, automation process made the user more efficient and more productive.

Moreover, according to authors Hose, Mitrani, and Olmstead (2004), their research system allowed assigning programs for presentation in a digital cinema. To generate a schedule that has decoding modules that control playback of data, a scheduler was implemented for presentation in digital cinema systems. This decoding module might operate in automatic or manual mode. In automatic mode, the decoding module controls playback based on the schedule without user intervention. In manual mode, the decoding module cues the user at the appropriate times to control the playback based on the schedule.

According to Hampson and Witkowski (2016), a mechanism that identified and analyzed the user's past interactions with advertisements, and used this analysis for advertisement selection. This used the analysis to intelligently inform advertisement selection and presented the selected ad to the user in conjunction

with the requested video. Past users could interact with the advertisement displayed in watching ads without skipping it; could share and could comment on the ads; could like or upvote an ad; and could visit or subscribe to a channel.

According to Sprogis (2004), video data scheduling was a system that includes a computer storage unit used for storing digital video data of video information; a plurality of digital projector assemblies that was coupled to the computer storage unit; and a scheduled input unit that was for receiving show schedule information. This included the plurality of start times and locations which each plurality of shows are scheduled to begin. The system also disclosed a production unit that was for assembling presentation data. This included a subset of a content data, with the presentation data being associated with the first show.

As hundreds or thousands of video clips were being delivered and reproduced, data behaviour might not be efficient when scheduled from time to time. It required organizing and plotting schedules in a specific area and time one by one. Manual video scheduling could lead to more errors without knowing in time which might affect the overall process of work. Automated scheduling of videos for each allotted time slot might lessen the issues and might give them earlier warning to know that there was an existing error that needs to be fixed.

At the end, videoclips that would be released at each scheduled time were more plotted and organized with the use of automation. Work was done with efficiency while delivering with more data covered, issues fixed, and runnable.

2.1 COMPARISON MATRIX

Table 1

Comparison Matrix

Functionalities	Automation of Fashion Show Playlist for Fashion One Inc	Application of Automated Video Analysis to Road User Behaviour	Automated Playlist Generation	Presentation Scheduling on Digital Cinema	Intelligent Advertisement Selection	Video Data Scheduling System
Analyze video	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO
Scheduling of shows	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES
Calculate videoclip duration	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
Play on Air	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
User interaction	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Analyze schedule	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Generate a new schedule	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
Classify videoclips by class.	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

CHAPTER 3

TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

In today's uncertain economy, companies were looking for ways to make their organization run more efficiently, became more competitive in saving money, and provided employees with tools to make them as productive as possible. Fashion One Inc. used manuals for their video clips scheduling process. It took time, effort, and frequent errors with this process. Especially, they were catering thousands of video clips to schedule and to obtain for their work everyday. Here are some technologies and their usage and benefits that we used in this study.

This referred to software that ran through browsers like Google Chrome. The system only needed an intranet to access it and could be used by a specific assigned employee/Admin. Automated Playlist was a web application which could be accessed only in the Fashion One Inc. . Its purpose was to automate the scheduling of video clips.

Intranet Site

An intranet site is a mini-Internet accessed through Web browsers. It is typically running on private local area networks (LAN) rather than public Web servers. Users could only access it when they were inside the premises of the company. Automation of Fashion Show Video Playlist System was a great example for this because this system could only be accessed in Fashion One Inc. Today, modern intranet is now much more than a place to store static corporate content—it was becoming a key tool for organizational success. The intranet was generally a one-way knowledge disperser used solely by central management and leading markets (James, 2006). New intranet was about exploiting web technology in an organisational context so that the users could

better utilize the intranet from a knowledge management perspective(Stenmark, 2002).

Laravel

Useful in easing common tasks used in the majority of web projects such as authentication, routing, sessions, and caching. This aimed to make the development process be more pleasing for the developer without sacrificing application functionality.

Back-end Framework

Back- end Framework is defined as the subordinate processor or program (not directly accessible by users), which performs a specialized function on behalf of a main processor or software system. It consists of tools and languages used in server-side programming in a web development environment. An ideal backend framework is taken care of by many developers which is involved in tracking bugs, applying patches, and keeping the fellow developers informed.

Jquery

This took a lot of common tasks that required many lines of JavaScript code to accomplish and wrapped them into methods that you could call with a single line of code. Managing annotations on large sets of annotatable code elements in a consistent manner would allow developers to make greater use of annotations and gain greater access to the benefits they provide (Bradley, 2008).

Bootstrap

A great opportunity for the researchers to use this because this is an open-source framework that combines HTML, CSS, and JavaScript code to help developers build web applications. This could be used for desktop and mobile development, so it could really be considered as user friendly.

Front-end framework

Front-end Framework is also known as “CSS frameworks”. These are packages containing pre-written, standardized code in files and folders. Typically, front-end frameworks contain the following components: A grid which makes it simple to organize the design elements of your website and defined font styles and sizing. The need for a front-end new version of the application on potentially thousands of client computers, made cross-platform compatibility support easy to accomplish.

XAMPP

XAMPP is a simple, lightweight Apache distribution that is extremely easy for developers to create a local web server for testing and deployment purposes. It stood for Cross-Platform (X), Apache (A), MariaDB (M), PHP (P) and Perl (P).

Database connectivity

Connecting to a database via PHP is an extremely important step to connect for a successful query. RDBMS is a DBMS designed specifically for relational databases that refers to a database that stores data in a structured format, using rows and columns for easy access and managing data.

PhpMyAdmin

PhpMyAdmin is a free software tool to handle Internet administration only of MySQL databases. It allows for a wide range of operations, including database management, as well as table, field, relation, index, user, and permission changes.

Font Awesome

It is one of the popular ways to add font icons to your website. The icons were created using scalable vectors, so you can use high quality icons that work well on any screen size.

Bitbucket

It is a web-based version control repository hosting service for source code and development projects that use either Mercurial (since launch) or Git.

CHAPTER 4

DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter presented the conceptual structure of what the project proponents would do and the collection of procedures, techniques, tools, and documentation aids which would help the proponents in their effort to solve computing problems. It would also help the project proponent plan, manage, control and evaluate computing research projects.

4.1 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework. The user used a personal computer to create a show or movie schedule and then inputted the schedule in the application. The web application would then analyze the show schedule and generate a video clips playlist based on the show schedule.

4.2 Analysis and Design

Figure 2. Entity Relationship Diagram. The user, supplier, and show could have one or many clips but the clip could only have one user, supplier and show. The log and srt can only have one clip but the clip could have zero or many log, srt and ratings. The category, pg_ratings and class could have zero or many clips but clip could only have one category, pg_ratings and class. The clip_language could have one or many clips and language.

4.3 Development Model

Figure 3. V-Model. The proponents used V-Model Methodology because it was easy to manage due to the rigidity of the model. Each phase had specific deliverables and a reviewed process which would ensure the quality, reliability and maintainability of the application. V-Model composed of three group phase the Verification Phases, Coding Phase, and Validation Phases. Verification phases were: Requirement Analysis which is where the product requirements were understood from the customer's perspective, System Design was the understanding and detailing the complete hardware and communication setup for the product under development, Architectural Design was the system design broken down further into modules taking up different functionality, Module Design was the detailed internal design for all the system modules is specified. Coding Phase was the actual coding of the system modules designed in the design phase and performed based on the coding guidelines and standards. Validation Phases were: Unit Testing was the testing at code level and helped eliminate

bugs at an early stage, Integration Testing was performed to test the coexistence and communication of the internal modules within the system, System Testing check the entire system functionality and the communication of the system under development with external systems and Acceptance Testing uncovered the compatibility issues with the other systems available in the user environment and discovered the non-functional issues such as load and performance error in the actual user environment.

4.4 Development Approach

Figure 4. Top-Down Approach. The proponent used Top-Down Development Approach in developing the system because of the characteristic of this approach which progress was made by defining required elements in terms of more basic elements and defining the undefined elements every previous phase that was defined to the next phase which was useful in our development to generate new solution or ideas in each phase.

4.5 Software Development Tools

Table 2

Software Development Tools

Name	Version	Source	Use
Visual Studio Code	1.28	https://code.visualstudio.com/	Software for coding
Laravel	5.7	https://laravel.com/	Back-end framework
Google Chrome	70.0.3538	https://google.com	Browser for simulation
Bootstrap	4.1	https://getbootstrap.com	Front-end framework
XAMPP	7.2.11	https://www.apachefriends.org/index.html	Database connectivity
PhpMyAdmin	4.8.3	https://www.phpmyadmin.net	Database Implementation
Git	2.19.1	https://git-scm.com	Code tracking
Font Awesome	5.5	https://fontawesome.com/	Front-end framework
Jquery	3.3.1	https://jquery.com	Front-end Framework
Bitbucket		https://bitbucket.org	Repository

4.6 Project Management

Project management was a method of organizing all activities related to a project and its parts. The purpose of Project Management was to practice initiating, planning, executing, controlling, and closing the work of a team to achieve specific goals and meet specific success criteria at the specified time. It

was also the way a person organizes and manages resources that were necessary to complete a project.

4.6.1 Schedule and Timeline

Table 3

1st Semester 2018

Tasks	August 1 - August 31	September 3 - September 28	October 1 - October 30	November 3 - November 29	December 1 - December 15
Initial Meeting of Members					
Assign Team Lead					
Look for the Adviser					
Meeting with the Adviser					
Look for the Client					
Meeting with the Client					
Gathering of Requirements					
Discussion of the Initial Plan					
Discussion of the Proposed System					
Documentation					
Documentation of the Chapter 1					
Documentation of the Chapter 2					
Documentation of the Chapter 3					
Documentation of the Chapter 4					
Review and Finalize Documentation of Chapter 1 to Chapter 4					
Documentation Defense					
Pre-defense					
Final defense					
Approval of the proposed system					

Chart of the system. This showed the amount of work done or production complete in certain periods of time in relation to the amount planned for those periods.

Table 4

2nd Semester 2018 - 2019

Task	January	February	March	April	May
Coding					
Coding of Front-end					
Coding of Back-end					
Documentation					
Chapter 5					
Chapter 6					
Testing					
Validate					
Revise					
Deployment					
Approved System					

The project schedule of the system. This showed the documentation, coding and testing phase of the whole schedule. The duration showed the working days of the specific tasks.

4.6.2 Responsibilities

Table 5

Responsibilities

Task	Khim	Jomar	Racquel	Razel
Documentations	S	S	S	L
Back-End	S	L	S	S
Front-End	L	S	S	S
Testing and Reviews	S	S	L	S

The table showed the responsibilities/task of each member.

S - Support = assist in accomplishing the tasks.

L - Leader = main responsible in accomplishing the tasks.

4.6.3 Budget and Cost Management

Table 6

Project Budget and Cost in Development Phase

Expense	Unit	Cost Per Unit	Estimated Cost
Internet	3hrs/day	₱ 10.00/hour	₱ 600.00
Transportation	50(4 students)	₱ 7.00	₱ 1,400.00
Book Binding	3 Books	₱ 405.00	₱ 1, 215.00
User manuals	5 books	₱ 50.00	₱ 250.00
Document Printing	3 copies	₱ 50.00	₱ 150.00
TOTAL			₱ 3, 615.00

Project Budget and Cost in Development of the System. It also showed the resources of the proponents used during the development and documentation of the system. Operation stage and Implementation did not cost anything as everything was provided for free by the Passerelles Numeriques.

4.7 Verification, Validation and Testing

VERIFICATION

Verification was a process that would control whether the system that the proponents were making was right. In this study, the proponents recapped what the proponents did in order to verify if they were doing the right project. These were the following below. At least 4 black-box testers.

VALIDATION

Validating your system helped you improve the quality and authenticity of your project. Validation is a process which answers the question “Are we building the right system?” In a company this process has always been integrated in developing a project or a certain system. The proponents in this project used these things to help validate the project. At least 20 programmers would do the verification.

- **User acceptance testing**

In this study, we would likely conduct a test that would answer our question “Would the user like to use the system?” In this way proponents can evaluate their proposed system. The application has 2 types of user the administrator and the scheduler. There should be at least one user to test the functionality and behavior of administrator user type and 6 users to test the scheduler user type.

- **Usability testing**

Usability testing involves getting people from the target audience to evaluate your site whilst performing tasks. In this way we would be able to know if our system’s usability was acceptable, especially the UI.

CHAPTER 5

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Systems Capability

- The system is capable of generating video clips based on the scheduled categories inputted by the user.
- The system is capable of calculating video clips durations.
- The system can generate video playlists that contain inserted ads and fillers.
- The system was capable of looking for the right clip at the right place and at the right time, to lessen time and effort, to increase productivity, and to avoid human failures.

5.2 Major Modules

The proposed system has the following major modules:

- Clips Module- contains the following:
 - Category- a module that enables the user to add and to show different categories.
 - PG Ratings-a module that enables the user to add PG ratings.
 - SRT- a module that enables the user to add subtitles
 - Server- a module that enables the user to add two server countries - Philippines and Russia.
- Language Module- a module that enables the user to add language.
- Playlist - a module that enables the user to add playlist either manual input or upload a file.

5.3 Verification (Black Box Testing)

The Automation of Fashion Show Video Playlist for Fashion One Inc. system was tested from April 15, 2019 –April 25, 2019 by the following testers:

- Rinalyn Bonajos
- Jaya Althea Lazo
- Randel Pagligaran
- Fresca Joyce Olila

After executing a test, the decision is defined according to the following rules:

- Acceptable – The test sheet is set to "Acceptable" status if the actual result meets the expected result.
- Not Acceptable - The test sheet is set to "Not Acceptable" status if the actual result does not meet the expected result.

Table 7

Test Cases

Automation of Fashion Show Video Playlist for Fashion One INC.						
Functionality Testing						
Name of Tester:		Date Finished:				
Date Started:		Date Finished:				
USE CASE NO & DESCRIPTION	Test Case No.	Description	Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Status
	TST_No_01_01	Allow the user to search the IP Address of the application	1. Open a Google Chrome web browser 2. Input localhost:8000 3. Click Enter key	Login Page should be displayed.	Login Page is displayed.	✓
	TST_No_01_02	Allow the user login the application	1. Enter valid email address in the required field 2. Enter password in the required field 3. Click Login button	Home Page should be displayed with the following data: - About us - Video clips displayed - number of users - Fashion Show Playlist Schedule	Home Page is displayed with the following data: - About us - Video clips displayed - number of users - Fashion Show Playlist Schedule	✓
USE_CASE_02_Home	TST_No_02_01	Display the following menus	1. Click Home menu button	The following menu should be displayed:	The following menu is displayed:	✓
	TST_No_02_02	Display the following menus	1. Click the add user button	User should be navigated to add user modal screen.	User is navigated to add user modal screen.	✓
USE_CASE_03_Users	TST_No_03_01	Allow the user to add a user	1. Click Users left-hand menu 2. Click Add User button 3. Populate the required Name field 4. Populate the required Email field 5. Select Role from dropdown field 6. Populate the required Password field 7. Populate the same password in the required Confirm Password field 8. Click Submit button	User should be added in the Users list and displayed with the following columns: - User ID - Name - Email - Role - Action	User is added in the Users list and displayed with the following columns: - User ID - Name - Email - Role - Action	✓
	TST_No_03_02	Allow the user to edit the user item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit user name 3. Click Update button	User name should be updated.	User name is updated.	✓
	TST_No_03_03	Allow the user to delete an item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	The item should be deleted.	The item is deleted.	✓

USE_CASE_04_Clips	TST_No_04_01	Allow the user to add a clips	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Clips left-hand menu 2. Click Add Clips button 3. Populate the following required textfields: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Title - Duration - Date Received - Supplier 4. Populate the following dropdown fields: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Category - Language - PG Ratings - SRT - Music - Server 5. Click Submit button 	Clips should be added in the Clips list and be displayed with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clips ID - Title - Duration - Date added - Added by - Action 	Clips is added in the Clips list and be displayed with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clips ID - Title - Duration - Date added - Added by - Action 	
	TST_No_04_02	Allow the user to edit a clips	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit clip 3. Click Update button 	Items should be updated.	Clip item is updated.	
	TST_No_04_03	Allow the user to delete a clips	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button 	The item should be deleted.	The item is deleted.	
USE_CASE_05_Playlist	TST_No_05_01	Allow the user to input a schedule manually	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Playlist left-hand menu 2. Click Manual button 3. Populate the required Start Time field 4. Populate the required End Time field 5. Click Submit button 	Manual Scheduling should be displayed.	Manual Scheduling is displayed.	
	TST_No_05_02	Allow the user to generate a playlist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Select Category Name in all dropdown field 2. Click Generate Playlist button 	Video Clips Playlist should be displayed.	Video Clips Playlist is displayed.	
	TST_No_05_03	Allow the user to download the playlist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Download CSV button 	CSV file should be downloaded.	CSV file is downloaded.	
	TST_No_05_04	Allow the user to generate the playlist automatically	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Choose File button 2. Select CSV file from the computer 3. Click Open button 4. Click Submit button 	Video Clips Playlist should be displayed.	Video Clips Playlist is displayed.	
	TST_No_05_05	Allow the user to download the generated Video Clips Playlist	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Download CSV button 	CSV file should be downloaded.	CSV file is downloaded.	

USE_CASE_06_Category	TST_No_06_01	Allow the user to add a Category	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Category left-hand menu 2. Click Add Category button 3. Populate the required Category Name field 4. Click Submit button 	Category should be added and displayed in Categories list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Category ID - Name - Date Added - Added By - Number of Clips - Action 	Category is added and displayed in Categories list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Category ID - Name - Date Added - Added By - Number of Clips - Action 	
	TST_No_06_02	Allow the user to edit the category item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit the category name 3. Click Update button 	Category Name should be updated.	Category Name is updated.	
	TST_No_06_03	Allow the user to delete the category item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button 	Category item should be deleted.	Category item should be deleted.	
USE_CASE_07_Language	TST_No_07_01	Allow the user to add a language	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Language left-hand menu 2. Click Add Language button 3. Populate the required Language Name field 4. Click Submit button 	Language should be added and displayed in Languages list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Language ID - Language Name - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action 	Language should be added and displayed in Languages list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Language ID - Language Name - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action 	
	TST_No_07_02	Allow the user to edit the language item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit the language name 3. Click Update button 	Language name should be updated.	Language name should be updated.	
	TST_No_07_03	Allow the user to delete the language item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button 	Language item should be deleted.	Language item should be deleted.	
USE_CASE_08_PG Ratings	TST_No_08_01	Allow the user to add a PG Ratings	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click PG Ratings left-hand menu 2. Click Add PG Ratings button 3. Populate the required PG Rating Name field 4. Click Submit button 	PG Ratings should be added and displayed in PG Ratings list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PG Ratings ID - PG Ratings - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action 	PG Ratings should be added and displayed in PG Ratings list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PG Ratings ID - PG Ratings - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action 	

	TST_No_08_02	Allow the user to edit the PG Rating item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit PG Rating Name 3. Click Update button 	Category name should be updated.	Category name is updated.	
	TST_No_08_03	Allow the user to delete the PG Rating item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button 	Category/item should be deleted.	Category/item is deleted.	
USE_CASE_09_SRT	TST_No_09_01	Allow the user to add a SRT	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click Add SRT button 2. Populate the required SRT Name field 3. Click Submit button 	SRT should be added and displayed in the Subtitles list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SRT ID - SRT - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action 	SRT should be added and displayed in the Subtitles list with the following columns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SRT ID - SRT - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action 	
	TST_No_09_02	Allow the user to edit the SRT item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit SRT name 3. Click Update button 	SRT name should be updated.	SRT name should be updated.	
	TST_No_09_03	Allow the user to delete the SRT item	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button 	SRT item should be deleted.	SRT item should be deleted.	

USE_CASE_10_Music	TST_No_10_01	Allow the user to add a Music	1. Click Music left-hand menu 2. Click Add Music button 3. Populate the required Music Name 4. Click Submit button	Music should be added and displayed in the Musics list with the following columns: - Music ID - Music - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	Music is added and displayed in the Musics list with the following columns: - Music ID - Music - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	
	TST_No_10_02	Allow the user to edit the Music item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Music name 3. Click Update button	Music item should be updated.	Music item is updated.	
	TST_No_10_03	Allow the user to delete the Music item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Music item should be deleted.	Music item is deleted.	
USE_CASE_11_Servers	TST_No_11_01	Allow the user to add a server	1. Click Servers left-hand menu 2. Click Add Server button 3. Populate the required Server Name 4. Select one or more Language/s from required dropdown field 5. Select one or more Restricted PG Ratings from required dropdown field 6. Click Submit button	Server should be added and displayed in Servers list with the following columns: - Server ID - Server - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	Server is added and displayed in Servers list with the following columns: - Server ID - Server - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	
	TST_No_11_02	Allow the user to edit the server item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit server name 3. Click Submit button	Server item should be updated.	Server item is updated.	
	TST_No_11_03	Allow the user to delete the server item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Server item should be deleted.	Server item is deleted.	
USE_CASE_12_Advertisement	TST_No_12_01	Allow the user to add an advertisement	1. Click Advertisement left-hand menu 2. Click Add Advertisement button 3. Populate the required Advertisement Name field 4. Click Submit button	Advertisement should be added and displayed in Advertisements list with the following columns: - Advertisement ID - Advertisement Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	Advertisement is added and displayed in Advertisements list with the following columns: - Advertisement ID - Advertisement Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	
	TST_No_12_02	Allow the user to edit the advertisement item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Advertisement Name 3. Click Update button	Advertisement item should be updated.	Advertisement item is updated.	
	TST_No_12_03	Allow the user to delete the advertisement item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Advertisement item should be deleted.	Advertisement item is deleted.	
USE_CASE_13_Filler	TST_No_13_01	Allow the user to add a filler	1. Click Filler left-hand menu 2. Click Add Filler button 3. Populate the required Filler Name 4. Click Submit button	Filler should be added and displayed in Fillers list with the following columns: - Filler ID - Filler Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	Filler is added and displayed in Fillers list with the following columns: - Filler ID - Filler Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	
	TST_No_13_02	Allow the user to edit the filler item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Filler Name 3. Click Update button	Filler item should be updated.	Filler item is updated.	
	TST_No_13_03	Allow the user to delete the filler item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Filler item should be deleted.	Filler item is deleted.	
USE_CASE_14_Logout	TST_No_14_01	Allow the user to logout from the app	1. Click on the user(admin/user) link on the top right corner of the home screen. 2. Choose "logout" in the dropdown.	User(admin/user) should be navigated to login page	User(admin/user) is navigated to login page	

This table shows the 36 test cases. This is the bases of the testers to verify if the steps match on the behavior of the application.

Figure 5. Pie Chart. Out of the 36 test cases, the general result had 6 not acceptable which is equivalent to 16.7% and 30 acceptable which was equivalent to 83.33%. Six (6) not acceptable results were mainly because of the performance of the system when overloaded with data it slowed the fetching of the data in the database. This affected in user, clips and playlist module. Thirty (30) acceptable results were analyzed as passed because it met the clients requirements. Proponents did not proceed to User Acceptance Testing until not acceptable was fixed and were focusing on major functionalities and modules which were clips module and playlist module which focused on generating video clips playlist.

5.4 Validation (User Acceptance Testing)

Table 8

Table Summary Formula

Table Summary		Average Score Interpretation:
Criteria	Total Score	
1. Functionality	Total score ÷ no. of sub-questions	4.1 – 5.0 = Very Acceptable 3.1 – 4.0 = Acceptable 2.1 – 3.0 = Moderately Acceptable 1.0 – 2.0 = Not Acceptable
2. Reliability	Total score ÷ no. of sub-questions	
3. Usability	Total score ÷ no. of sub-questions	
4. Efficiency	Total score ÷ no. of sub-questions	
5. Maintainability	Total score ÷ no. of sub-questions	
6. Support and Manuals	Total score ÷ no. of sub-questions	

This table showed the formula on how to compute the average total score interpretation in validating the system.

Table 9

Validation Results of Average Score Interpretation

Table Summary	
Criteria	Total Score
Functionality	4.05
Reliability	3.92
Usability	3.93
Efficiency	3.99
Maintainability	4.12
Support and Manuals	3.72
Average Total Score	3.95

This table showed the result scores of the 6 different criterias in validating the system. General analysis based on tester’s inputted comments of each criteria in terms of Functionality which only had average score of 4.05 are the following as for the validators: Much better that the display for clips were from the newest and oldest clips. But overall, the main functionality worked as what was expected applies in the system. Reliability had an average score of 3.92 because the performance of the system was slow when fetching data in the clips module and language module. Usability had an average score of 3.93 because it affected the performance of the application when trying to load the system when fetching big data. This applied in the major modules like clips module and playlist module. Efficiency gathered 3.99 because although the system is good, it still needed more improvement especially in performance and only required minimal hardware resources and this applies in the whole system. Maintainability scores 4.12 as for what the validators observed that the application was working but not perfect as this reflect on the other criteria for the major modules like clips module and playlist, and minor modules like language, server, PG ratings, advertisement and fillers modules. The Support and Manuals gathered the average score of

3.72 because manuals were provided in this documents and has screenshots in each module which serves as a user guide of the application.

Figure 6. Bar Graph. This graph showed the average total score interpretation on how the system's functionality , reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability and support manuals works according to its current score over the total summary of user criteria. This reflected on the previous table that showed the average total score interpretation. Functionality which only had average score of 4.05 referred to the capability and suitability of a of the system in the major modules which were clips module, and playlist module. Reliability which had an average score of 3.92 because of an accurate result of a measurement, calculation, or specification in generating the clips modules. Usability had an average score of 3.93 because of the degree to which our system is able or fit to be used in all modules. Efficiency gathered 3.99 because it was capable of producing desired results on time in generating playlist in playlist module. Maintainability scored 4.12 as for what the validators observed that the application was understood, repaired, or enhanced in the whole application system. Support and Manuals gathered the average score of 3.72 because manuals were provided in this documents and had screenshots which served as a user guide of the application for the admin and users side.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Summary

The findings in this research entitled Automation of Fashion Show Video Playlist of Fashion One Inc. that automation of video clips to generate is better than the manual process. The result of this research helped the client to validate, generate and calculate video clips schedule automatically. The system was capable of looking for the right clip at the right place and at the right time, to lessen time and effort, to increase productivity, and to avoid human failures. The system

also provided an efficient and reliable performance output to our client in Fashion One Incorporated by generating an automated video clips scheduling playlist. As already explained in the manual process, it was very prone that human errors sometimes occur from time to time and that was what they were trying to avoid.

6.2 Conclusions

Based on the study implemented, automated scheduling of video clips and playlists were created for the client in Fashion One Inc. This helps employees in making a fashion video playlist to look for the right clip at the right place and at the right time. It also helps lessen the time, effort and human errors. That was to change the manual process to an automated one. This is specifically intended and created for the Fashion One Inc. but these findings could be useful to Television Network, Researchers and other Future Researchers. Different ways of approach to effectively lessen the burden of work. Our system is unique as it has many related systems but the whole functionality and process in it differs the most, as it contains videoclips to generate video playlist scheduling with a calculated time duration. These findings are not inline with other related work. Though some parts are similar. Like some related systems are more on

automation but not involved in scheduling or involved in scheduling but not generally automate or generate video clips playlist.

Time and effort invested in this application should be more than enough to sustain on the client's side as it also required more time to create a whole and perfect system. This system is useful as the proponents assure that this is not just working as of today but it can still be used for future purposes. The automation implemented is adapting in any advance evolution of technology compared to manual processes , which is very delayed in coping up behaviors of technologies nowadays.

6.3 Recommendations

As our system Automation of Fashion Show Video Playlist of Fashion One Inc. has a lot more to improve and to develop, proponents and other users recommend the following for possible enhancement of our system.

- For better performance, application hosting needs a high-end server or at least domain for accessing the application.
- This system is only limited to the Fashion One Inc. company via local host, as for benefits of other related companies which may prefer online, better if it can be accessed through internet for a faster and easier way when this can be used for bigger companies.
- Much better if the system will display not just an automated playlist but also a whole 15 min. mp4 video.

GLOSSARY

Analyze is to study or examine something carefully in a methodical way, typically for purposes of explanation and interpretation.

Automate is to make a process in a factory or office operate by machines or computers, in order to reduce the amount of work done by humans

Automation is the use of largely automatic equipment in a system of manufacturing or other production process.

Coding guidelines are also known as coding standards. It gives a uniform appearance to the codes written by different engineers. It enhances code understanding. This lists several rules to be followed during coding, such as the way variables are to be named, the way the code is to be laid out, error return conventions, others.

Computer storage is a device that is used for storing, porting and extracting data files and objects. It can hold and store information both temporarily and permanently, and can be internal or external to a computer, server or any similar computing device.

Conceptual structure is an autonomous level of cognitive representation in representing concepts in terms of a small number of conceptual primitives.

Cross-platform is a product or system that can work across multiple types of platforms or operating environments. This is able to be used on different types of computers or with different software packages.

Data-driven means that progress in an activity is compelled by data, rather than by intuition or by personal experience.

Duration is defined as the length of time that something lasts.

Fashion show is a show at which people who design clothes show their new designs and is about expressing your identity, showing someone who you are through your fashion choices and using your clothes to tell someone something about you.

Generate this means to produce or create. This also means to produce (a set or sequence of items) by performing specified mathematical or logical operations on an initial set.

Human failures also known as human error means that something has been done that was "not intended by the actor; not desired by a set of rules or an external observer; or that led the task or system outside its acceptable limits.

Intranet is a private network that is contained within an enterprise. It may consist of many interlinked local area networks and also use leased lines in the wide area network. The main purpose of an intranet is to share company information and computing resources among employees.

Local host is a hostname that means 'this computer'. It is used to access the network services that are running on the host via the loopback network interface. Using the loopback interface bypasses any local network interface hardware.

Manual is relating to use or do with the hands without any automated interventions.

Mechanism is a part of a machine, or a set of parts that work together or a way of doing something that is planned or part of a system.

Micro data have often been collected from each individual through a survey or interview. This is a unit-level data that obtained from sample surveys, censuses, and administrative systems.

Modules is a part of a program that are composed of one or more independently developed modules that are not combined until the program is linked. A single module can contain one or several routines. In hardware, a module is a self-contained component.

Show schedule is a plan of show that gives a list of events or tasks and the times at which each one should happen or be done.

Technology is a science or knowledge put into practical use to solve problems or invent useful tools.

V-model is an SDLC model where execution of processes happens in a sequential manner in a V-shape. It is also known as Verification and Validation model. It is an extension of the waterfall model and is based on the association of a testing phase for each corresponding development stage.

Validation is the action of making or declaring something legally or officially acceptable.

Verification is the process of establishing the truth, accuracy, or validity of something.

Video clips are short clips of video, usually part of a longer recording. The term is also more loosely used to mean any short video less than the length of a traditional television program.

Video playlist is a list of URLs to videos on selected websites. This also identify as an index of selected videos on a website such as YouTube. For example, YouTube provides lists of videos of popular artists.

Web application is an application program that is stored on a remote server and delivered over the Internet through a browser interface.

Web server is a program that uses HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol) to serve the files that form Web pages to users, in response to their requests, which are forwarded by their computers' HTTP clients server software, or hardware dedicated to running said software, that can satisfy World Wide Web client requests.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

“Automated Playlist Generation”. Kshitij Kumar (2012). Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20120284744A1>.

“Presentation scheduling in digital cinema system”. Jesse Hose, Michael Mitrani and Roger Olmstead (2004). Available at <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20030048418A1>.

“Application of Automated Video Analysis to Road User Behaviour”. Aliaksei Laureshyn (2010). Retrieved from <http://portal.research.lu.se/portal/files/5337337/1522970.pdf>

“Intelligent Advertisement Selection”. Courtney Hampson and Mary Witkowski (2016). Available at https://www.tdcommons.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=&httpsredir=1&article=1362&context=dpubs_series

“Video Data Scheduling System”. Sprogis David H. (1999). Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20040078268A1/en>

“Automatic Generation of Effective Video Summaries”. Johannes Sasongko (2011). Retrieved from https://eprints.qut.edu.au/45473/1/Johannes_Sasongko_Thesis.pdf

“Web Front-End for student data analysis application”. Jonas Vaclavek (2015). Retrieved from https://dspace.cvut.cz/bitstream/handle/10467/61632/F3-BP-2015-Vaclavek-Jonas-vaclavek_zaverecna_prace.pdf

“JQuery-Based Refactorings as a Framework for Managing Java Annotations”. Alex Bradley (2008) . Retrieved from <https://www.cs.ubc.ca/~awjb/pubs/bsc-thesis.pdf>

“Electronic television program guide schedule system and method”. Gerald Bennington, George backer, Shawn Green, Bill Cooper, Dave Spell, Bruce Davis and Michael Morris (2006) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US7100185B2/en?q=video&q=scheduling&q=system&oq=video+scheduling+system>

“Tag-based scheduling system for digital communication switch”. Hugh Lauer, Shia Shen and Abhijit Ghosh (1995) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US5455825A/en?q=video&q=scheduling&q=system&oq=video+scheduling+system&page=4>

“Video recorder scheduling”. Peter Vogel (2002) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20020184636A1/en?q=video&q=scheduling&q=system&oq=video+scheduling+system&page=9>

“Television system with scheduling of advertisements”. Michael Ellis and Daniel Hagenbuch (2004) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20040194131A1/en?q=advertisement&q=scheduling&oq=advertisement+scheduling>

“Data storage management and scheduling system”. James Barton and Bryan Beach (2002) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2000059223A1/en?q=video&q=scheduling&q=system&oq=video+scheduling+system&page=24>

“Detecting and distributing video content identities”. Joseph Matthews,

James Baldwin and David Rogers Treadwell (2012) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20120324495A1/en?q=received&q=schedule&q=video&q=presentation&oq=received+and+schedule+a+video+presentation+&page=14>

“Program planning management system”. Lloyd Smith and Edward Balunas (1997) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US6609100B2/en?q=fashion&q=show&q=scheduling&q=system&oq=fashion+show+scheduling+system&page=9>

“System and method for generating an advertising schedule”. Benjamin Verschueren, Michael Woellmer, Stephen Angelovich, David Rabinowitz, Sarah Doraski and Monique Roy (2007) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20070113244A1/en?q=advertisement&q=scheduling&q=system&oq=advertisement+scheduling+system+>

“System and method for scheduling in-theatre advertising”. Christopher Theiste, Joseph Agee and Thomas Schmidt (2004) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20040181819A1/en?q=advertisement&q=scheduling&q=system&oq=advertisement+scheduling+system+>

“TV schedule system and process”. Patrick Young (1987) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US4706121A/en?q=received&q=schedule&q=video&q=presentation&oq=received+and+schedule+a+video+presentation+&page=4>

“Management of television presentation recordings”. Harold Plourde and Mark Adams (2007) . Retrieved from <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20030154484A1/en?q=received&q=schedule>

[e&q=video&q=presentation&oq=received+and+schedule+a+video+presentation+&page=14](#)

“Designing the new intranet”. Dick Stenmark (2002) . Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.122.6448&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

APPENDICES

Appendix A

TRANSMITTAL LETTER

May 9, 2019

John Rexter Flores
Web Supervisor

Fashion One Inc.
Lapu-Lapu, Cebu,

Dear Mr. Flores,

Greetings!

May we request from you the permission to gather information from you and the Fashion One Inc. for our research study entitled "**AUTOMATION OF FASHION SHOW VIDEO PLAYLIST FOR FASHION ONE INC.**".

The above research study is a requirement for the completion of the degree in Certificate in Computer Technology in the University of San Carlos. I am

confident that the result of the study would be useful and helpful in the betterment of the community.

Thank you very much. I am looking for your positive response.

Respectfully yours,

Khim Cole

Jomar Edaño

Maria Razel Inoc

Racquel Rosel

Endorsed by:

John Rexter Flores

Capstone Adviser

Approved by:

John Rex Paña

Class Adviser/ Instructor

Appendix B

INTERVIEW GUIDE

1. What was the main problem on why you chose this study?
2. Why was this content important to know?
3. How sure were you that this research would be useful in the future? Why?
4. What was the most stressful part about working on your capstone project?
5. Were you now able to apply this concept in this everyday world? Why?
6. What have you learned about completing this phase of your capstone project?
7. Why was this study important to you?

ANSWERS

1. The main problem of Fashion One Inc. was that they were doing a manual process in scheduling videoclips to play shows everyday. They received thousands of video clips each day and that they needed and looked for an efficient way to do the task.
2. This study was not just focusing on our present needs but it also adopted the evolving technologies nowadays. When Fashion One Inc., could be able to use this automated system in the future, the production of their company might be doubled or more than that. Thus, their success might be greater, too. Also, there were related companies that might benefit this system when implemented.
3. As what had been discussed, this study was not just focusing on our present needs but it also adopted the growing technology of our society. As time passed by, manual handling of projects nowadays might not be as useful as automated systems.
4. One of the most stressful parts in doing this capstone proposal documents was like being tied up between On the Job Trainings and this project documents. This research was our key to reach the next step to comply with our student life. Even when having no sleep for the whole night from work the whole day. When you could see your hard work be paid, then those sleepless nights to make our projects and stressful days at work weren't a waste. It inspired us to do a lot more from doubting ourselves that we can't.
5. Yes, in fact, we could all apply this concept to our everyday life as long as this is good and beneficial in IT industries and in any related businesses. Also, as a proponent, we did not see anything wrong in this research because on our side, we could benefit in terms of our studies, we could use our specializations and other soft skills, and most of all, we could contribute to our society and help the company with their existing problems.

6. Aside from doing this project as a team, no matter how confident we were in gathering our data and sharing expertise with this project, we still weren't comfortable enough that we could really deliver all the data that the panel needed because of some circumstances. But, we, as a team, were doing our best to comply with all these with extra effort and dedication.

7. This study was important to us. This helped both parties into a win-win situation. They offered us the project that we needed for this phase of our student life and at the same time we were also helping them to develop their said new process of the company if this system would be implemented.

Appendix C

Modules	Functionality
Admin	Admin is allowed to do any activities in the application
Masterlist of Users	Allow to create, read, delete and update users
Masterlist of Playlist	Allow to generate fashion show video playlists
Masterlist of Clips	Allow to create, read, delete and update clips
Masterlist of Category	Allow to create, read, delete and update category
Masterlist of Language	Allow to create, read, delete and update language
Masterlist of PG Ratings	Allow to create, read, delete and update PG Ratings
Masterlist of SRT	Allow to create, read, delete and update SRT

Masterlist of Server	Allow to create, read, delete and update Server
Masterlist of Advertisement	Allow to create, read, delete and update Advertisement
Masterlist of Bumpers	Allow to create, read, delete and update bumpers
User	User is not allowed to view other user and cannot generate playlist
Masterlist of Clips	Allow to create, read and update users
Masterlist of Category	Allow to create, read and update category
Masterlist of Language	Allow to create, read and update language
Masterlist of PG Ratings	Allow to create, read and update PG ratings
Masterlist of SRT	Allow to create, read and update SRT

Masterlist of Server	Allow to create, read and update server
Masterlist of Advertisement	Allow to create, read and update advertisement
Masterlist of Bumpers	Allow to create, read and update bumpers
Application	
Generate playlist	The system is capable to generate a fashion show video playlist schedule
search clips	The system has a clips search option that allows to look for the clips added in the application
Web access/ localhost/ web browser	This system is only accessible via web browsers/ localhost

Appendix D

Automation of Fashion Show Video Playlist for Fashion One INC.							
Functionality Testing							
Name of Tester: Unknown							
Date Started:							
Date Finished:							
USE CASE NO & DESCRIPTION	Test Case No.	Description	Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Status	Comments/ Recommendations
USE_CASE_01 Login	TST_No_01_01	Allow the user to search the IP Address of the application	1. Open a Google Chrome web browser 2. Input localhost:8000 3. Click Enter key	Login Page should be displayed.	Login Page is displayed.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_01_02	Allow the user login the application	1. Enter valid email address in the required field 2. Enter password in the required field 3. Click Login button	Home Page should be displayed with the following data: - About us - Video clips displayed - number of users - Fashion Show Playlist Schedule	Home Page is displayed with the following data: - About us - Video clips displayed - number of users - Fashion Show Playlist Schedule	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_02 Home	TST_No_02_01	Display the following menus	1. Click Home menu button	The following menu should be displayed.	The following menu is displayed.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_03 Users	TST_No_03_01	Allow the user to add a user	1. Click Users left-hand menu 2. Click Add User button 3. Populate the required Name field 4. Populate the required Email field 5. Select Role from dropdown field 6. Populate the required Password field 7. Populate the same password in the required Confirm Password field 8. Click Add User button	User should be added in the Users list and displayed with the following columns: - User ID - Name - Email - Role - Action	User is added in the Users list and displayed with the following columns: - User ID - Name - Email - Role - Action	NOT ACCEPTABLE	Can't add user
	TST_No_03_02	Allow the user to edit the user item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit user name 3. Click Update button	User name should be updated.	User name is updated.	NOT ACCEPTABLE	Can't add user
	TST_No_03_03	Allow the user to delete an item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	The item should be deleted.	The item is deleted.	NOT ACCEPTABLE	Can't add user
USE_CASE_04 Clips	TST_No_04_01	Allow the user to add a clips	1. Click Clips left-hand menu 2. Click Add Clip button 3. Populate the following required textfields: - Title - Duration - Date Received - Supplier 4. Populate the following dropdown fields: - Category - Language - PG Ratings - SRT - Music - Server 5. Click Add Clip button	Clips should be added in the Clips list and be displayed with the following columns: - Clips ID - Title - Duration - Date added - Added by - Action	Clips is added in the Clips list and be displayed with the following columns: - Clips ID - Title - Duration - Date added - Added by - Action	NOT ACCEPTABLE	Clips are displayed but does not load immediately which causes UI displayed text to truncate.
	TST_No_04_02	Allow the user to edit a clips	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit clip 3. Click Update button	Items should be updated.	Clip item is updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_04_03	Allow the user to delete a clips	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	The item should be deleted.	The item is deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_05 Playlist	TST_No_05_01	Allow the user to input a schedule manually	1. Click Playlist left-hand menu 2. Click Manual button 3. Populate the required Start Time field 4. Populate the required End Time field 5. Click Submit button	Manual Scheduling should be displayed.	Manual Scheduling is displayed.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_05_02	Allow the user to generate a playlist	1. Select Category Name in all dropdown field 2. Click Generate Playlist button	Video Clips Playlist should be displayed.	Video Clips Playlist is displayed.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_05_03	Allow the user to download the playlist	1. Click Download CSV button	CSV file should be downloaded.	CSV file is downloaded.	NOT ACCEPTABLE	Very loading and it affects the performance testing.
USE_CASE_06 Category	TST_No_06_01	Allow the user to add a Category	1. Click Category left-hand menu 2. Click Add Category button 3. Populate the required Category Name field 4. Click Add Category button	Category should be added and displayed in Categories list with the following columns: - Category ID - Name - Date Added - Added By - Number of Clips - Action	Category is added and displayed in Categories list with the following columns: - Category ID - Name - Date Added - Added By - Number of Clips - Action	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_06_02	Allow the user to edit the category item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit the category name 3. Click Update button	Category Name should be updated.	Category Name is updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_06_03	Allow the user to delete the category item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Category item should be deleted.	Category item should be deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_07 Language	TST_No_07_01	Allow the user to add a language	1. Click Language left-hand menu 2. Click Add Language button 3. Populate the required Language Name field 4. Click Add Language button	Language should be added and displayed in Languages list with the following columns: - Language ID - Language Name - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	Language should be added and displayed in Languages list with the following columns: - Language ID - Language Name - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_07_02	Allow the user to edit the language item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit the language name 3. Click Update button	Language name should be updated.	Language name is updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_07_03	Allow the user to delete the language item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Language item should be deleted.	Language item should be deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_08 PG Ratings	TST_No_08_01	Allow the user to add a PG Ratings	1. Click PG Ratings left-hand menu 2. Click Add PG Ratings button 3. Populate the required PG Rating Name field 4. Click Add PG Ratings button	PG Ratings should be added and displayed in PG Ratings list with the following columns: - PG Ratings ID - PG Ratings - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	PG Ratings should be added and displayed in PG Ratings list with the following columns: - PG Ratings ID - PG Ratings - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_08_02	Allow the user to edit the PG Rating item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit PG Rating Name 3. Click Update button	Category name should be updated.	Category name is updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_08_03	Allow the user to delete the PG Rating item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Category item should be deleted.	Category item is deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	

USE_CASE_09_SRT	TST_No_09_01	Allow the user to add a SRT	1. Click Add SRT button 2. Populate the required SRT Name field 3. Click Add SRT button	SRT should be added and displayed in the Subtitles list with the following columns: - SRT ID - SRT - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	SRT should be added and displayed in the Subtitles list with the following columns: - SRT ID - SRT - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_09_02	Allow the user to edit the SRT item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit SRT name 3. Click Update button	SRT name should be updated.	SRT name should be updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_09_03	Allow the user to delete the SRT item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	SRT item should be deleted.	SRT item should be deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_11_Servers	TST_No_11_01	Allow the user to add a server	1. Click Servers left-hand menu 2. Click Add Server button 3. Populate the required Server Name 4. Select one or more Language/s from required dropdown field 5. Select one or more Restricted PG Ratings from required dropdown field 6. Click Add Server button	Server should be added and displayed in Servers list with the following columns: - Server ID - Server - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	Server is added and displayed in Servers list with the following columns: - Server ID - Server - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_11_02	Allow the user to edit the server item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit server name 3. Click Submit button	Server item should be updated.	Server item is updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_11_03	Allow the user to delete the server item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Server item should be deleted.	Server item is deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_12_Advertisement	TST_No_12_01	Allow the user to add an advertisement	1. Click Advertisement left-hand menu 2. Click Add Advertisement button 3. Populate the required Advertisement Name field 4. Click Add Advertisement button	Advertisement should be added and displayed in Advertisements list with the following buttons: - Advertisement ID - Advertisement Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	Advertisement is added and displayed in Advertisements list with the following buttons: - Advertisement ID - Advertisement Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_12_02	Allow the user to edit the advertisement item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Advertisement Name 3. Click Update button	Advertisement item should be updated.	Advertisement item is updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_12_03	Allow the user to delete the advertisement item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Advertisement item should be deleted.	Advertisement item is deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_13_Filler	TST_No_13_01	Allow the user to add a filler	1. Click Filler left-hand menu 2. Click Add Filler button 3. Populate the required Filler Name field 4. Click Add Filler button	Filler should be added and displayed in Filler list with the following columns: - Filler ID - Filler Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	Filler is added and displayed in Filler list with the following columns: - Filler ID - Filler Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	NOT ACCEPTABLE	It adds filler but the added filler does not reflect automatically
	TST_No_13_02	Allow the user to edit the filler item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Filler Name 3. Click Update button	Filler item should be updated.	Filler item is updated.	ACCEPTABLE	
	TST_No_13_03	Allow the user to delete the filler item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Filler item should be deleted.	Filler item is deleted.	ACCEPTABLE	
USE_CASE_14_Logout	TST_No_14_01	Allow the user to logout from the app	1. Click on the user(admin/user) link on the top right corner of the home screen. 2. Choose "logout" in the dropdown.	User(admin/user) should be navigated to login page	User(admin/user) is navigated to login page	ACCEPTABLE	

Automation of Fashion Show Video Playlist for Fashion One INC.

Functionality Testing

Name of Tester:

Date Started:

Date Finished:

USE CASE NO & DESCRIPTION	Test Case No.	Description	Test Procedure	Expected Results	Actual Results	Status
USE_CASE_01_Login	TST_No_01_01	Allow the user to search the IP Address of the application	1. Open a Google Chrome web browser 2. Input localhost:8000 3. Click Enter key	Login Page should be displayed.	Login Page is displayed.	✓
	TST_No_01_02	Allow the user login the application	1. Enter valid email address in the required field 2. Enter password in the required field 3. Click Login button	Home Page should be displayed with the following data: - About us - Video clips displayed - number of users - Fashion Show Playlist Schedule	Home Page is displayed with the following data: - About us - Video clips displayed - number of users - Fashion Show Playlist Schedule	✓
USE_CASE_02_Home	TST_No_02_01	Display the following menus	1. Click Home menu button	The following menu should be displayed:	The following menu is displayed:	✓
	TST_No_02_02	Display the following menus	1. Click the add user button	User should be navigated to add user modal screen.	User is navigated to add user modal screen.	✓
USE_CASE_03_Users	TST_No_03_01	Allow the user to add a user	1. Click Users left-hand menu 2. Click Add User button 3. Populate the required Name field 4. Populate the required Email field 5. Select Role from dropdown field 6. Populate the required Password field 7. Populate the same password in the required Confirm Password field 8. Click Submit button	User should be added in the Users list and displayed with the following columns: - User ID - Name - Email - Role - Action	User is added in the Users list and displayed with the following columns: - User ID - Name - Email - Role - Action	✓
	TST_No_03_02	Allow the user to edit the user item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit user name 3. Click Update button	User name should be updated.	User name is updated.	✓
	TST_No_03_03	Allow the user to delete an item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	The item should be deleted.	The item is deleted.	✓
USE_CASE_04_Clips	TST_No_04_01	Allow the user to add a clips	1. Click Clips left-hand menu 2. Click Add Clips button 3. Populate the following required textfields: - Title - Duration - Date Received - Supplier 4. Populate the following dropdown fields: - Category - Language - PG Ratings - SRT - Music - Server 5. Click Submit button	Clips should be added in the Clips list and be displayed with the following columns: - Clips ID - Title - Duration - Date added - Added by - Action	Clips is added in the Clips list and be displayed with the following columns: - Clips ID - Title - Duration - Date added - Added by - Action	✓
	TST_No_04_02	Allow the user to edit a clips	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit clip 3. Click Update button	Items should be updated.	Clip item is updated.	✓
	TST_No_04_03	Allow the user to delete a clips	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	The item should be deleted.	The item is deleted.	✓
USE_CASE_05_Playlist	TST_No_05_01	Allow the user to input a schedule manually	1. Click Playlist left-hand menu 2. Click Manual button 3. Populate the required Start Time field 4. Populate the required End Time field 5. Click Submit button	Manual Scheduling should be displayed.	Manual Scheduling is displayed.	✓
	TST_No_05_02	Allow the user to generate a playlist	1. Select Category Name in all dropdown field 2. Click Generate Playlist button	Video Clips Playlist should be displayed.	Video Clips Playlist is displayed.	✓
	TST_No_05_03	Allow the user to download the playlist	1. Click Download CSV button	CSV file should be downloaded.	CSV file is downloaded.	✓
	TST_No_05_04	Allow the user to generate the playlist automatically	1. Click Choose File button 2. Select CSV file from the computer 3. Click Open button 4. Click Submit button	Video Clips Playlist should be displayed.	Video Clips Playlist is displayed.	✓
	TST_No_05_05		1. Click Download CSV button	CSV file should be downloaded.	CSV file is downloaded.	✓
			1. Click Categories left-hand menu	Categories should be added and displayed	Categories is added and displayed in	✓

USE_CASE_07_Language	TST_No_07_01	Allow the user to add a language	1. Click Language left-hand menu 2. Click Add Language button 3. Populate the required Language Name field 4. Click Submit button	Language should be added and displayed in Languages list with the following columns: - Language ID - Language Name - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	Language should be added and displayed in Languages list with the following columns: - Language ID - Language Name - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action		
	TST_No_07_02	Allow the user to edit the language item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit the language name 3. Click Update button	Language name should be updated.	Language name should be updated.		
	TST_No_07_03	Allow the user to delete the language item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Language item should be deleted.	Language item should be deleted.		
USE_CASE_08_PG_Ratings	TST_No_08_01	Allow the user to add a PG Ratings	1. Click PG Ratings left-hand menu 2. Click Add PG Ratings button 3. Populate the required PG Rating Name 4. Click Submit button	PG Ratings should be added and displayed in PG Ratings list with the following columns: - PG Ratings ID - PG Ratings - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	PG Ratings should be added and displayed in PG Ratings list with the following columns: - PG Ratings ID - PG Ratings - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action		
	TST_No_08_02	Allow the user to edit the PG Rating item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit PG Rating Name 3. Click Update button	Category name should be updated.	Category name is updated.		
	TST_No_08_03	Allow the user to delete the PG Rating item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Category item should be deleted.	Category item is deleted.		
USE_CASE_09_SRT	TST_No_09_01	Allow the user to add a SRT	1. Click Add SRT button 2. Populate the required SRT Name field 3. Click Submit button	SRT should be added and displayed in the Subtitles list with the following columns: - SRT ID - SRT - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	SRT should be added and displayed in the Subtitles list with the following columns: - SRT ID - SRT - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action		
	TST_No_09_02	Allow the user to edit the SRT item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit SRT name 3. Click Update button	SRT name should be updated.	SRT name should be updated.		
	TST_No_09_03	Allow the user to delete the SRT item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	SRT item should be deleted.	SRT item should be deleted.		
USE_CASE_10_Music	TST_No_10_01	Allow the user to add a Music	1. Click Music left-hand menu 2. Click Add Music button 3. Populate the required Music Name 4. Click Submit button	Music should be added and displayed in the Musics list with the following columns: - Music ID - Music - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	Music is added and displayed in the Musics list with the following columns: - Music ID - Music - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action		
	TST_No_10_02	Allow the user to edit the Music item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Music name 3. Click Update button	Music item should be updated.	Music item is updated.		
	TST_No_10_03	Allow the user to delete the Music item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Music item should be deleted.	Music item is deleted.		
USE_CASE_11_Servers	TST_No_11_01	Allow the user to add a server	1. Click Servers left-hand menu 2. Click Add Server button 3. Populate the required Server Name 4. Select one or more Language/s from required dropdown field 5. Select one or more Restricted PG Ratings from required dropdown field 6. Click Submit button	Server should be added and displayed in Servers list with the following columns: - Server ID - Server - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action	Server is added and displayed in Servers list with the following columns: - Server ID - Server - Date Added - Added By - Count - Action		
	TST_No_11_02	Allow the user to edit the server item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit server name 3. Click Submit button	Server item should be updated.	Server item is updated.		
	TST_No_11_03	Allow the user to delete the server item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Server item should be deleted.	Server item is deleted.		
USE_CASE_12_Advertisement	TST_No_12_01	Allow the user to add an advertisement	1. Click Advertisement left-hand menu 2. Click Add Advertisement button 3. Populate the required Advertisement Name field 4. Click Submit button	Advertisement should be added and displayed in Advertisements list with the following columns: - Advertisement ID - Advertisement Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	Advertisement is added and displayed in Advertisements list with the following columns: - Advertisement ID - Advertisement Name - Date Added - Added By - Action		
	TST_No_12_02	Allow the user to edit the advertisement item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Advertisement Name 3. Click Update button	Advertisement item should be updated.	Advertisement item is updated.		
	TST_No_12_03	Allow the user to delete the advertisement item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Advertisement item should be deleted.	Advertisement item is deleted.		
USE_CASE_13_Filler	TST_No_13_01	Allow the user to add a filler	1. Click Filler left-hand menu 2. Click Add Filler button 3. Populate the required Filler Name field 4. Click Submit button	Filler should be added and displayed in Fillers list with the following columns: - Filler ID - Filler Name - Date Added - Added By - Action	Filler is added and displayed in Fillers list with the following columns: - Filler ID - Filler Name - Date Added - Added By - Action		
	TST_No_13_02	Allow the user to edit the filler item	1. Click edit icon button 2. Edit Filler Name 3. Click Update button	Filler item should be updated.	Filler item is updated.		
	TST_No_13_03	Allow the user to delete the filler item	1. Click delete icon button 2. Click Confirm button	Filler item should be deleted.	Filler item is deleted.		
USE_CASE_14_Logout	TST_No_14_01	Allow the user to logout from the app	1. Click on the user/admin/user link on the top right corner of the home screen. 2. Choose "Logout" in the dropdown.	User(admin/user) should be navigated to login page	User(admin/user) is navigated to login page		

Appendix E

Name: Tester 1																			
Criteria	Description	Rating (1 – Lowest / 5 – Highest)																	
		1	2	3	4	5													
1. Functionality																			
1.1 Accuracy	How does the system adequately meet its objectives ?				✓														
1.2 Security	How protected is the system and its data contents from unauthorized access ?				✓														
2. Reliability																			
2.1 Data Validity	Does the system check and validate user input to avoid erroneous data entry ?				✓														
2.2 Recoverability	How easily does the system provide a way to back-up data stored in it ?				✓														
3. Usability																			
3.1 Understandability	Does the system provide on-screen instructions ?				✓														
3.2 Learnability	Can users quickly and easily learn to use the software ?				✓														
3.3 Operability	Can users easily navigate between program screens ?					✓													
3.4 Attractiveness	Is the overall user interface visually pleasing ?				✓														
4. Efficiency																			
4.1 Ease of Start-up	How easily is the system started up ?				✓														
4.2 Resource Utilization	Does the system require minimal hardware resources ?		✓																
4.3 Time Behaviour	How quickly does the system accomplish specific actions ?					✓													
5. Maintainability																			
5.1 Installability	How easily is the system installed (in case re-installation is needed) ?				✓														
5.2 Testability	Can the system be tested and verified using test/sample data ?					✓													
6. Support and Manuals																			
6.1 Understandability	Does the user manual provide clear and concise instructions on how to operate the software ?				✓														
6.2 Visual References	Does the user manual provide actual screenshots showing how to operate the software ?				✓														
Comments / Suggestions																			
1. Functionality																			
2. Reliability																			
3. Usability																			
4. Efficiency	Not really necessary requires minimal hardware resources																		
5. Maintainability																			
6. Support and Manuals																			
<p style="text-align: center;">NOTE: Total score / no. of questions</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Table Summary</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin: 0 auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 70%; padding: 5px;">Criteria</th> <th style="width: 30%; padding: 5px;">Total Score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr style="background-color: #d9ead3;"> <td style="padding: 5px;">Functionality</td> <td style="text-align: center; padding: 5px;">4.5</td> </tr> <tr style="background-color: #d9ead3;"> <td style="padding: 5px;">Reliability</td> <td style="text-align: center; padding: 5px;">4</td> </tr> <tr style="background-color: #d9ead3;"> <td style="padding: 5px;">Usability</td> <td style="text-align: center; padding: 5px;">4.25</td> </tr> <tr style="background-color: #d9ead3;"> <td style="padding: 5px;">Efficiency</td> <td style="text-align: center; padding: 5px;">3.66</td> </tr> <tr style="background-color: #d9ead3;"> <td style="padding: 5px;">Maintainability</td> <td style="text-align: center; padding: 5px;">4.5</td> </tr> <tr style="background-color: #d9ead3;"> <td style="padding: 5px;">Support and Manuals</td> <td style="text-align: center; padding: 5px;">4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						Criteria	Total Score	Functionality	4.5	Reliability	4	Usability	4.25	Efficiency	3.66	Maintainability	4.5	Support and Manuals	4
Criteria	Total Score																		
Functionality	4.5																		
Reliability	4																		
Usability	4.25																		
Efficiency	3.66																		
Maintainability	4.5																		
Support and Manuals	4																		

Name: Tester 2						
Criteria	Description	Rating (1 – Lowest / 5 – Highest)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1. Functionality						
1.1 Accuracy	How does the system adequately meet its objectives ?				✓	
1.2 Security	How protected is the system and its data contents from unauthorized access ?			✓		
2. Reliability						
2.1 Data Validity	Does the system check and validate user input to avoid erroneous data entry ?			✓		
2.2 Recoverability	How easily does the system provide a way to back-up data stored in it ?				✓	
3. Usability						
3.1 Understandability	Does the system provide on-screen instructions ?			✓		
3.2 Learnability	Can users quickly and easily learn to use the software ?		✓			
3.3 Operability	Can users easily navigate between program screens ?			✓		
3.4 Attractiveness	Is the overall user interface visually pleasing ?			✓		
4. Efficiency						
4.1 Ease of Start-up	How easily is the system started up ?			✓		
4.2 Resource Utilization	Does the system require minimal hardware resources ?				✓	
4.3 Time Behaviour	How quickly does the system accomplish specific actions ?				✓	
5. Maintainability						
5.1 Installability	How easily is the system installed (in case re-installation is needed) ?				✓	
5.2 Testability	Can the system be tested and verified using test/sample data ?				✓	
6. Support and Manuals						
6.1 Understandability	Does the user manual provide clear and concise instructions on how to operate the software ?		✓			
6.2 Visual References	Does the user manual provide actual screenshots showing how to operate the software ?		✓			
Comments / Suggestions						
1. Functionality	Much better that the display for clippings is from the newest and oldest clippings					
2. Reliability						
3. Usability						
4. Efficiency						
5. Maintainability						
6. Support and Manuals						
NOTE: Total score / no. of questions						
Table Summary						
Criteria		Total Score				
Functionality		3.2				
Reliability		3.2				
Usability		2.75				
Efficiency		3.66				
Maintainability		4				
Support and Manuals		2				

Name: Tester 3						
Criteria	Description	Rating (1 – Lowest / 5 – Highest)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1. Functionality						
1.1 Accuracy	How does the system adequately meet its objectives ?					✓
1.2 Security	How protected is the system and its data contents from unauthorized access ?					
2. Reliability						
2.1 Data Validity	Does the system check and validate user input to avoid erroneous data entry ?				✓	
2.2 Recoverability	How easily does the system provide a way to back-up data stored in it ?				✓	
3. Usability						
3.1 Understandability	Does the system provide on-screen instructions ?				✓	
3.2 Learnability	Can users quickly and easily learn to use the software ?				✓	
3.3 Operability	Can users easily navigate between program screens ?				✓	
3.4 Attractiveness	Is the overall user interface visually pleasing ?				✓	
4. Efficiency						
4.1 Ease of Start-up	How easily is the system started up ?				✓	
4.2 Resource Utilization	Does the system require minimal hardware resources ?				✓	
4.3 Time Behaviour	How quickly does the system accomplish specific actions ?				✓	
5. Maintainability						
5.1 Installability	How easily is the system installed (in case re-installation is needed) ?				✓	
5.2 Testability	Can the system be tested and verified using test/sample data ?				✓	
6. Support and Manuals						
6.1 Understandability	Does the user manual provide clear and concise instructions on how to operate the software ?				✓	
6.2 Visual References	Does the user manual provide actual screenshots showing how to operate the software ?					✓
Comments / Suggestions						
1. Functionality	The main Functionality work as what is expected					
2. Reliability	The system did not really have enough validation					
3. Usability						
4. Efficiency	The system is good but needs more improvement specially in performance.					
5. Maintainability						
6. Support and Manuals						
NOTE: Total score / no. of questions						
Table Summary						
Criteria		Total Score				
Functionality		4.5				
Reliability		4				
Usability		4				
Efficiency		4				
Maintainability		4				
Support and Manuals		4.5				

Name: Tester 4						
Criteria	Description	Rating (1 – Lowest / 5 – Highest)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1. Functionality						
1.1 Accuracy	How does the system adequately meet its objectives ?					✓
1.2 Security	How protected is the system and its data contents from unauthorized access ?				✓	
2. Reliability						
2.1 Data Validity	Does the system check and validate user input to avoid erroneous data entry ?				✓	
2.2 Recoverability	How easily does the system provide a way to back-up data stored in it ?				✓	
3. Usability						
3.1 Understandability	Does the system provide on-screen instructions ?				✓	
3.2 Learnability	Can users quickly and easily learn to use the software ?				✓	
3.3 Operability	Can users easily navigate between program screens ?				✓	
3.4 Attractiveness	Is the overall user interface visually pleasing ?					✓
4. Efficiency						
4.1 Ease of Start-up	How easily is the system started up ?				✓	
4.2 Resource Utilization	Does the system require minimal hardware resources ?					✓
4.3 Time Behaviour	How quickly does the system accomplish specific actions ?				✓	
5. Maintainability						
5.1 Installability	How easily is the system installed (in case re-installation is needed) ?				✓	
5.2 Testability	Can the system be tested and verified using test/sample data ?				✓	
6. Support and Manuals						
6.1 Understandability	Does the user manual provide clear and concise instructions on how to operate the software ?				✓	
6.2 Visual References	Does the user manual provide actual screenshots showing how to operate the software ?					✓
Comments / Suggestions						
1. Functionality						
2. Reliability						
3. Usability						
4. Efficiency						
5. Maintainability						
6. Support and Manuals						
NOTE: Total score / no. of questions						
Table Summary						
Criteria		Total Score				
Functionality		4				
Reliability		4.5				
Usability		4.75				
Efficiency		4.66				
Maintainability		4				
Support and Manuals		4.4				

Tester 1

Table Summary

Criteria	Total Score
Functionality	4.5
Reliability	4
Usability	4.25
Efficiency	3.66
Maintainability	4.5
Support and Manuals	4

Tester 2

Table Summary

Criteria	Total Score
Functionality	3.2
Reliability	3.2
Usability	2.75
Efficiency	3.66
Maintainability	4
Support and Manuals	2

Tester 3

Table Summary

Criteria	Total Score
Functionality	4.5
Reliability	4
Usability	4
Efficiency	4
Maintainability	4
Support and Manuals	4.5

Tester 4

Table Summary

Criteria	Total Score
Functionality	4
Reliability	4.5
Usability	4.75
Efficiency	4.66
Maintainability	4
Support and Manuals	4.4

SYSTEM'S INSTALLATION MANUAL

1.1. System Requirements

Hardware	Software
1. Computer	1. php
	2. Server
	3. mySQL database
	4. composer
	5. nodeJS
	6. laravel
	7. git
	8. XAMMP

1.2. Installation

- Install node JS, Xampp and composer.
- Make a folder in your computer.
- Open your gitlab and cmd.
- Clone code in your folder using cmd.
- Perform the following command after git clone:
 - >composer install
 - >copy .env.example .env
 - >php artisan key:generate
 - >php artisan serve
- Open your local host.

To create a user:

Open your command and perform the following:

```
php artisan tinker
```

Create a new user (use whatever fields you need e.g. `username`, `email`)

```
$user = new User;  
$user->username = 'admin';  
$user->name = 'admin';  
$user->password = Hash::make('password');  
$user->save();
```

For .env file in the database

```
DB_CONNECTION=mysql  
DB_HOST=127.0.0.1  
DB_PORT=3306  
DB_DATABASE=homestead  
DB_USERNAME:root  
DB_PASSWORD:
```

USER MANUAL

Application IP Address

Login Page

Home Page

User Page

Add User

Edit User Item

Delete User Item

Click Cancel button

Click Confirm button

Click Delete Icon button

Clips Page

Click Clips left-hand menu

Add Clips

Click Add Clips button

Input Title

Input Video Clip Duration

Input Date

Select Category

Select PG Rating

Select Server

Input Supplier name

Select Language

Select SRT

Upload Video Clip

Click Cancel button

Click Submit button

Search Clip Item

Edit Clip Item

Delete Clip Item

Playlist Page

The screenshot shows the FASHIONone interface. On the left, a dark sidebar contains a navigation menu with items: Home, Users, Clips, Playlist, Schedule, Video Clip Playlist, Category, Language, PG Ratings, SRT, Servers, Advertisement, and Filter. The 'Playlist' item is highlighted with a red box, and an arrow points to it from an orange callout box labeled 'Click Playlist left-hand menu'. Below it, the 'Schedule' sub-item is also highlighted with a red box, with an arrow pointing to it from another orange callout box labeled 'Click Schedule sub-menu'. The main content area is titled 'Select Scheduling Process' and has two buttons: 'Manual' and 'Input Excel File'. Below this is a 'Playlist' section with a 'Download CSV' button and a table. The table has columns for Start Time, End Time, Duration, and Material ID.

Start Time	End Time	Duration	Material ID
00:00:00	00:01:00	00:01:00	1
00:01:00	00:02:29	00:01:29	205cc0051ee4ffc
00:02:29	00:04:47	00:02:18	205cc0051ee100
00:04:47	00:06:27	00:01:40	265cc0051ee2ff
00:06:27	00:08:40	00:02:13	265cc0051ee180
00:08:40	00:10:12	00:01:32	275cc0051f02c96
00:10:12	00:11:41	00:01:29	275cc0051f02c96
00:11:41	00:13:25	00:01:44	275cc0051f13180
00:13:25	00:14:59	00:01:34	275cc0051f13708
00:14:59	00:15:00	00:00:01	27

Manual Input of Playlist Schedule

The screenshot shows the 'Manual' input process. A modal dialog box titled 'Input Time' is open over the 'Manual' button in the background. The dialog has a header 'Input Time' and a note 'This field use 24 hour format'. It contains two input fields: 'Start Time' with the value '00 : 00' and 'End Time' with the value '00 : 15'. Below the fields are 'Cancel' and 'Submit' buttons. Orange callout boxes with arrows point to these elements: 'Click Manual button' points to the 'Manual' button in the background; 'Input Start Time' points to the 'Start Time' field; 'Input End Time' points to the 'End Time' field; 'Click Submit button' points to the 'Submit' button; and 'Click Cancel button' points to the 'Cancel' button.

Upload Excel file Schedule

Click Input Excel File button

Select Server

Click Submit button

Upload Excel file

Click Cancel button

Start Time	End Time	Duration	Material ID
00:01:00	00:01:00	00:01:00	1
00:02:29	00:02:29	00:01:29	265cd0651ec4fcc
00:04:47	00:04:47	00:02:18	265cd0651ec160
00:06:22	00:06:22	00:01:35	265cd0651ec2ff
00:08:40	00:08:40	00:02:10	265cd0651ec160
00:10:12	00:10:12	00:01:32	275cd0651f02cc6
00:11:41	00:11:41	00:01:29	275cd0651f060a
00:13:25	00:13:25	00:01:44	275cd0651f10100
00:14:59	00:14:59	00:01:34	275cd0651f19708
00:14:59	00:15:00	00:00:01	27

Download Generated Video Clip Schedule

Click Download CSV button

Open downloaded CSV file

Start Time	End Time	Duration	Material ID
00:01:00	00:01:00	00:01:00	1
00:01:00	00:02:29	00:01:29	265cd0651ec4fcc
00:02:29	00:04:47	00:02:18	265cd0651ec160
00:04:47	00:06:22	00:01:35	265cd0651ec2ff
00:06:22	00:08:40	00:02:10	265cd0651ec160
00:08:40	00:10:12	00:01:32	275cd0651f02cc6
00:10:12	00:11:41	00:01:29	275cd0651f060a
00:11:41	00:13:25	00:01:44	275cd0651f10100
00:13:25	00:14:59	00:01:34	275cd0651f19708
00:14:59	00:15:00	00:00:01	27

View Generated Video Clip

The screenshot shows the FashionOne dashboard with a 'Video Playlist' window. The left-hand navigation menu has 'Video Clip Playlist' highlighted. An orange callout box with an arrow points to this menu item, containing the text 'Click Video Clip Playlist sub-menu'. The main content area displays a grid of video thumbnails, each with a play button, a progress bar, and a star icon. The titles of the videos are partially visible, including 'Polaroid bi-directional Invera...', 'Blake Lively CFI FRRITY PRO...', 'Naomi Campbell CFI FRRITY ...', 'Fva i categoria Celebrity Profile...', 'Naomi Campbell CELEBRITY ...', 'Rosario Dawson Celebrity Pr...', 'Bradley Cooper CELEBRITY ...', and 'David Gandy CELEBRITY PR...'.

Category Page

The screenshot shows the FashionOne dashboard with the 'Category' page. The left-hand navigation menu has 'Category' highlighted. An orange callout box with an arrow points to this menu item, containing the text 'Click Category left-hand menu'. The main content area features a table titled 'Categories' with the following data:

Category ID	Name	Date Added	Added By	Number of Clips	Action
1	After Midnight	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
2	The Switch Ep 10	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
3	New York Fashion Week: Mens Spring/Summer 2019	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
4	Front Row	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
5	Beauty	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
6	Lifestyle	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	

Add Category

The screenshot shows the 'Add Category' modal in the FASHIONONE admin panel. The modal is a light brown box with a white background, containing a text input field for 'Category Name' and two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Confirm'. The background shows a table of existing categories.

Annotations:

- Click Add Category button
- Input Category Name
- Click Cancel button
- Click Confirm button

Category ID	Name	Added	Added By	Number of Clips	Action
1	After Midnight	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
2	The Switched 10	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
4	Front Row	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
5	Beauty	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
6	Lifestyle	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	

Edit Category Item

The screenshot shows the 'Edit Category' modal in the FASHIONONE admin panel. The modal is a light brown box with a white background, containing a text input field for 'Category Name' (pre-filled with 'After Midnight') and two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Confirm'. The background shows a table of existing categories with an edit icon highlighted.

Annotations:

- Edit Category name
- Click Cancel button
- Click Confirm button
- Click Edit Icon button

Category ID	Name	Added	Added By	Number of Clips	Action
1	After Midnight	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
2	The Switched 10	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
4	Front Row	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
5	Beauty	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
6	Lifestyle	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	

Delete Category Item

Categories

Delete Category

Delete Category After Midnight?

Cancel Confirm

Click Cancel button

Click Confirm button

Click Delete Icon button

Category ID	Name	Added	Added By	Number of Clips	Action
1	After Mid	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
4	Front Row	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
5	Beauty	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	
6	Lifestyle	2019-05-05 07:04:41		1920	

Language Page

Language

Click Language left-hand menu

User ID	Name	Email	Role	Action
3	Playlist User	playlistuser@gmail.com	Playlist	
4	Admin	admin@gmail.com	Administrator	

Add Language

The screenshot shows the 'Add Language' modal in the FASHION1one admin panel. The modal is titled 'Add Language' and contains a text input field labeled 'Language Name'. Below the input field are two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Submit'. The background shows a table of existing languages with columns for ID, Name, Added By, and Action.

ID	Name	Added By	Action
3	English	Admin	
4	Russian	Admin	

Annotations in the image include:

- Click Add Language button
- Input Language Name
- Click Cancel button
- Click Submit button

Edit Language Item

The screenshot shows the 'Edit Language' modal in the FASHION1one admin panel. The modal is titled 'Edit Language' and contains a text input field with 'English' entered. Below the input field are two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Update language'. The background shows the same table of existing languages as in the previous screenshot. The 'Action' column for the 'English' row has an edit icon highlighted.

ID	Name	Added By	Action
3	English	Admin	
4	Russian	Admin	

Annotations in the image include:

- Edit Language name
- Click Cancel button
- Click Update Language button
- Click Edit Icon button

Delete Language Item

Admin

Home

Users

Clips

Playlist

Category

Language

PG Ratings

SRT

Servers

Advertisement

Filler

Add Language

Languages

Delete Language

Delete Language English ?

ID	Name	Added By	Action
3	English	Admin	
4	Russian	Admin	

Cancel

Confirm

Click Cancel button

Click Confirm button

Click Delete icon button

PG Ratings Page

Admin

Home

Users

Clips

Playlist

Category

Language

PG Ratings

SRT

Filler

Add PG Ratings

PG Ratings

PG Ratings ID	PG Ratings	Date Added	Added By	Action
6	Rated G	2019-05-08 14:13:43	Admin	
7	Rated PG	2019-05-08 14:13:47	Admin	
8	Rated SPG	2019-05-08 14:13:51	Admin	
9	Junk Foods	2019-05-08 14:13:56	Admin	
10	Sexy	2019-05-08 14:14:00	Admin	

Click PG Ratings left-hand menu

Add PG Ratings

The screenshot shows the 'Add PG Rating' modal window. The modal has a title bar 'Add PG Rating' and a text input field labeled 'PG Rating Name'. Below the input field are two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Confirm'. The background shows a table of PG Ratings with columns: PG Ratings ID, PG Rating Name, Added By, and Action. The table contains rows with IDs 6, 7, 9, and 10.

PG Ratings ID	PG Rating Name	Added By	Action
6		Admin	
7	Rated PG	Admin	
9	Junk Foods	Admin	
10	Sexy	Admin	

Annotations in the image include:

- Click Add PG Ratings button (pointing to the 'Add PG Ratings' button in the sidebar)
- Input PG Rating Name (pointing to the text input field)
- Click Cancel button (pointing to the 'Cancel' button)
- Click Confirm button (pointing to the 'Confirm' button)

Edit PG Rating Item

The screenshot shows the 'Edit PG Rating' modal window. The modal has a title bar 'Edit PG Rating' and a text input field containing 'Rated G'. Below the input field are two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Update'. The background shows the same table of PG Ratings as in the first image. The 'Action' column for row ID 6 has an edit icon highlighted.

PG Ratings ID	PG Rating Name	Added By	Action
6	Rated G	Admin	
7	Rated PG	Admin	
10	Sexy	Admin	

Annotations in the image include:

- Edit PG Rating Name (pointing to the text input field)
- Click Cancel button (pointing to the 'Cancel' button)
- Click Update button (pointing to the 'Update' button)
- Click Edit Icon button (pointing to the edit icon in the table's action column)

Delete PG Rating Item

The screenshot shows the FASHIONONE PG Ratings management interface. A modal dialog titled "Delete PG Rating" is displayed, asking "Delete PG Rating Rated G?". The dialog has two buttons: "Cancel" and "Confirm". In the background, a table lists PG Ratings with columns for PG Ratings ID, Rated PG, Date Added, Added By, and Action. The "Action" column contains edit and delete icons. Three orange callout boxes with arrows point to the "Cancel" button, the "Confirm" button, and the delete icon in the table.

PG Ratings ID	Rated PG	Date Added	Added By	Action
6			Admin	[Edit] [Delete]
7	Rated PG	2019-05-08 14:13:4	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]
10	Sexy	2019-05-08 14:14:00	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]

Click Cancel button

Click Confirm button

Click Delete Icon button

SRT Page

The screenshot shows the FASHIONONE SRT (Subtitles) management interface. The left-hand menu is visible, with the "SRT" option highlighted. The main content area displays a table of subtitles with columns for SRT ID, SRT, Date Added, Added By, and Action. An orange callout box with an arrow points to the "SRT" option in the left-hand menu.

SRT ID	SRT	Date Added	Added By	Action
2	Fashion test	2019-05-08 14:14:17	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]
3	Artist Info	2019-05-08 14:53:51	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]
4	After Midnight Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:01	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]
5	The Switch Ep 10 Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]
6	New York Fashion Week: Mens Spring/Summer 2019 Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]
7	Front Row Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	[Edit] [Delete]

Click SRT left-hand menu

Add SRT

This screenshot illustrates the 'Add SRT' process. The interface shows a sidebar with navigation options and a main content area with a 'Subtitles' table. An 'Add SRT' button is highlighted in the sidebar. A modal window titled 'Add Subtitle' is open, containing fields for 'SRT Name', 'Select Language', and a 'Choose File' section with a 'Browse' button. 'Cancel' and 'Submit' buttons are at the bottom of the modal. Arrows point from text labels to these specific UI elements.

Click Add SRT Button

Input SRT Name

Select Language

Upload SRT file

Click Cancel Button

Click Submit Button

SRT ID	SRT	Date Added	Added By	Action
2	Fashion test	2019-05-08 14:53:51	Admin	
3	Artist Info	2019-05-08 14:53:51	Admin	
4	After Midnight	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	
5	The Switch Ep	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	
6	New York Fashion Week: Mens Spring/Summer 2019 Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	
7	Front Row Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	

Edit SRT Item

This screenshot illustrates the 'Edit SRT Item' process. The 'Subtitles' table is visible, and an 'Edit Subtitle' modal is open for the 'Fashion test' item. The modal contains fields for 'SRT Name' (pre-filled with 'Fashion test') and 'Select Language' (pre-filled with 'English'). It also has a 'Choose File' section with a 'Browse' button and 'Cancel' and 'Confirm' buttons at the bottom. An 'Edit' icon (pencil) is visible in the table's action column. Arrows point from text labels to these UI elements.

Edit SRT Name

Select Language

Click Edit Icon button

Upload SRT file

Click Confirm button

Click Cancel button

SRT ID	SRT	Date Added	Added By	Action
2	Fashion test	2019-05-08 14:14:17	Admin	
3	Artist Info	2019-05-08 14:53:51	Admin	
4	After Midnight	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	
5	The Switch Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	
6	New York Fashion Week: Mens Spring/Summer 2019 Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	
7	Front Row Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	

Delete SRT Item

The screenshot shows a 'Delete Subtitle' dialog box overlaid on a table of subtitles. The dialog box contains the text 'Delete subtitle Fashion test?' and two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Confirm'. The 'Cancel' button is highlighted with a red box and an arrow pointing to it from the label 'Click Cancel button'. The 'Confirm' button is also highlighted with a red box and an arrow pointing to it from the label 'Click Confirm button'. In the background table, the 'Delete' icon (a trash can) in the 'Action' column for the first row is highlighted with a red box and an arrow pointing to it from the label 'Click Delete Icon button'.

SRT ID	SRT	Date Added	Added By	Action
2	Fashion test	2019-05-08 14:14:17	Admin	[Delete]
3	Artist Info	2019-05-08 14:53:51	Admin	[Delete]
6	New York Fashion Week: Mens Spring/Summer 2019 Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	[Delete]
7	Front Row Subtitle English	2019-05-08 15:05:02	Admin	[Delete]

Servers Page

The screenshot shows the 'Servers' page in the FashionOne system. The left-hand navigation menu is visible, and the 'Servers' menu item is highlighted with a red box and an arrow pointing to it from the label 'Click Servers left-hand menu'. The main content area displays a table of servers.

Server ID	Server	Date Added	Added By	Languages	Prohibited PG Ratings	Action
3	Russia	2019-05-08 14:16:56	Admin	Russian	Junk Foods	[Edit] [Delete]
4	Philippines	2019-05-08 14:17:07	Admin	English	Sexy	[Edit] [Delete]

Add Server

The screenshot shows the 'Add Server' modal form overlaid on a 'Servers' table. The modal contains the following fields and buttons:

- Server Name**: A text input field.
- Select languages**: A dropdown menu.
- Prohibited PG Ratings**: A text input field.
- Cancel**: A button to close the modal.
- Submit**: A button to save the new server.

Annotations with arrows point to the following elements:

- Click Add Server button**: Points to the 'Add Server' button in the top left sidebar.
- Input Server Name**: Points to the 'Server Name' input field.
- Select Languages**: Points to the 'Select languages' dropdown.
- Input Prohibited PG Ratings**: Points to the 'Prohibited PG Ratings' input field.
- Click Cancel button**: Points to the 'Cancel' button.
- Click Submit button**: Points to the 'Submit' button.

Edit Server Item

The screenshot shows the 'Edit server' modal form overlaid on a 'Servers' table. The modal contains the following fields and buttons:

- Edit Server Name**: A text input field with 'Russia' entered.
- Edit Languages**: A dropdown menu with 'Russian' selected.
- Edit PG Ratings**: A text input field with 'Junk Foods' entered.
- Cancel**: A button to close the modal.
- Update**: A button to save the changes.

Annotations with arrows point to the following elements:

- Click Add Server button**: Points to the 'Add Server' button in the top left sidebar.
- Edit Server Name**: Points to the 'Edit Server Name' input field.
- Edit Languages**: Points to the 'Edit Languages' dropdown.
- Edit PG Ratings**: Points to the 'Edit PG Ratings' input field.
- Click Edit Icon button**: Points to the edit icon (pencil) in the 'Action' column of the 'Servers' table.
- Click Cancel button**: Points to the 'Cancel' button.
- Click Update button**: Points to the 'Update' button.

Delete Server Item

Click Cancel button

Click Confirm button

Click Delete Icon button

Server ID	Server	Languages	Prohibited PG Ratings	Action
3	Russia	Russian	Junk Foods	[Edit] [Delete]
4	Philippines	English	Sexy	[Edit] [Delete]

Advertisement Page

Click Advertisement left-hand menu

Advertisement ID	Advertisement Name	Date Added	Action
1	Beauty Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
2	After Midnight Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
3	Model Yoga Season 2 Ep2 Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
4	Style Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]
5	After Midnight Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]
6	Shades of Summer Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]

Add Advertisement

This screenshot shows the 'Add Advertisement' form in the FASHIONone admin panel. The form is overlaid on a table of existing advertisements. The table has columns for 'Advertisement ID', 'Date Added', and 'Action'. The 'Add Advertisement' form includes the following fields and buttons:

- Click Add Advertisement button**: Points to the 'Add Advertisement' button in the top left of the admin panel.
- Input Advertisement Name**: Points to the 'Advertisement Name' input field.
- Input Advertisement Duration**: Points to the 'Duration | 01 :00' input field.
- Upload Advertisement file**: Points to the 'Browse' button next to the 'Choose file' label.
- Click Cancel button**: Points to the 'Cancel' button at the bottom left of the form.
- Click Submit button**: Points to the 'Submit' button at the bottom right of the form.

Advertisement ID	Date Added	Action
1	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
2	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
3	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]
4	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]

Edit Advertisement Item

This screenshot shows the 'Edit Advertisement' form in the FASHIONone admin panel. The form is overlaid on a table of existing advertisements. The table has columns for 'Advertisement ID', 'Date Added', and 'Action'. The 'Edit Advertisement' form includes the following fields and buttons:

- Edit Advertisement Name**: Points to the 'Beauty Subtitle Ad' input field.
- Edit Advertisement Duration**: Points to the 'Duration | 01 :00' input field.
- Upload Advertisement file**: Points to the 'Browse' button next to the 'Choose file' label.
- Click Edit Icon button**: Points to the edit icon (pencil) in the 'Action' column of the table.
- Click Cancel button**: Points to the 'Cancel' button at the bottom left of the form.
- Click Update button**: Points to the 'Update' button at the bottom right of the form.

Advertisement ID	Date Added	Action
1	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
2	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
3	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]
4	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]
5	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]

Delete Advertisement Item

Click Delete Icon button

Click Cancel button

Click Confirm button

Advertisement ID	Advertisement	Date Added	Action
1	Beauty Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
2	After Midnight Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
3	After Midnight Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:00	[Edit] [Delete]
4	Style Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]
5	After Midnight Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]
6	Shades of Summer Subtitle Ad	2019-05-08 16:49:01	[Edit] [Delete]

Filler Page

Click Filler left-hand menu

Filler ID	Filler Name	Duration	Date Added	Action
2	Fashion a	00:00:30	2019-05-08 15:10:40	[Edit] [Delete]
3	Fashion b	00:00:48	2019-05-08 15:13:05	[Edit] [Delete]
4	Fashion c	00:00:15	2019-05-08 15:13:42	[Edit] [Delete]
5	Fashion d	00:00:32	2019-05-08 15:14:31	[Edit] [Delete]
6	Fashion e	00:00:03	2019-05-08 15:14:43	[Edit] [Delete]
7	Fashion f	00:00:44	2019-05-08 15:17:25	[Edit] [Delete]

Add Filler

The screenshot shows the 'Add Filler' modal window overlaid on a table of filler items. The modal contains the following elements:

- Click Add Filler button:** Points to the 'Add Filler' button in the top navigation bar.
- Input Filler Title:** Points to the text input field for the filler title.
- Input Filler Duration:** Points to the duration input field, currently showing '00:30'.
- Upload Filler file:** Points to the 'Browse' button next to the 'Choose File' label.
- Click Cancel button:** Points to the 'Cancel' button at the bottom left of the modal.
- Click Submit button:** Points to the 'Submit' button at the bottom right of the modal.

Filler ID	Filler Title	Duration	File	Created At	Action
2	Fashion a	00:30		2019-05-08 15:10:40	[Edit] [Delete]
3	Fashion b	00:30		2019-05-08 15:10:40	[Edit] [Delete]
4	Fashion c	00:30		2019-05-08 15:10:40	[Edit] [Delete]
5	Fashion d	00:00:32		2019-05-08 15:14:31	[Edit] [Delete]
6	Fashion e	00:00:03		2019-05-08 15:14:43	[Edit] [Delete]
7	Fashion e	00:00:44			[Edit] [Delete]

Edit Filler Item

The screenshot shows the 'Edit Filler' modal window overlaid on the same table of filler items. The modal contains the following elements:

- Edit Filler Title:** Points to the text input field containing 'Fashion a'.
- Edit Filler Duration:** Points to the duration input field containing '00:30'.
- Upload Filler file:** Points to the 'Browse' button next to the 'Choose File' label.
- Click Edit Icon button:** Points to the edit icon (pencil) in the 'Action' column of the table.
- Click Cancel button:** Points to the 'Cancel' button at the bottom left of the modal.
- Click Update button:** Points to the 'Update' button at the bottom right of the modal.

Filler ID	Filler Title	Duration	File	Created At	Action
2	Fashion a	00:30		2019-05-08 15:10:40	[Edit] [Delete]
3	Fashion b	00:30		2019-05-08 15:10:40	[Edit] [Delete]
4	Fashion c	00:30		2019-05-08 15:10:40	[Edit] [Delete]
5	Fashion d	00:00:32		2019-05-08 15:14:31	[Edit] [Delete]
6	Fashion e	00:00:03		2019-05-08 15:14:43	[Edit] [Delete]
7	Fashion e	00:00:44			[Edit] [Delete]

Delete Filler Item

Click Delete Icon button

Click Cancel button

Click Confirm button

Filler ID	Filler Name	Duration	Added	Action
2	Fashion a	00:00:48	2019-05-08 15:10:40	
3	Fashion b	00:00:48	2019-05-08 15:13:05	
4	Fashion c	00:00:48	2019-05-08 15:13:05	
5	Fashion d	00:00:32	2019-05-08 15:14:31	
6	Fashion e	00:00:03	2019-05-08 15:14:43	
7	Fashion f	00:00:44	2019-05-08 15:17:25	

Settings

Click Dropdown settings

User ID	Name	Email	Role	Action
3	Playlist User	playlistuser@gmail.com	Playlist	
4	Admin	admin@gmail.com	Administrator	

Profile Settings

This screenshot shows the 'Profile Settings' page in the FASHIONlone application. The left sidebar contains navigation items: Home, Users, Clips, Playlist, Category, Language, PG Ratings, SRT, Servers, Advertisement, and Filler. The main content area is titled 'Profile' and displays the user's name 'Admin' (Administrator) and statistics: Clips Added (41,601), Categories Added (0), and Servers Added (2). The 'Settings' section is active, showing a 'Reset Password' link and input fields for 'Name' (Admin) and 'Email' (admin@gmail.com). An 'Update' button is located below the email field. Annotations with arrows point to the 'Profile' menu item, the 'Settings' button, the 'Name' input field, the 'Email' input field, and the 'Update' button.

Click Profile menu item

Click Settings button

Edit Name

Edit Email Address

Click Update button

Profile Reset Password

This screenshot shows the 'Profile Reset Password' page in the FASHIONlone application. The left sidebar is identical to the previous screenshot. The main content area is titled 'Profile' and displays the user's name 'Admin' (Administrator) and statistics: Clips Added (48,001), Categories Added (0), and Servers Added (2). The 'Settings' section is active, showing a 'Reset Password' link and input fields for 'Password' and 'Confirm Password'. An 'Update' button is located below the 'Confirm Password' field. Annotations with arrows point to the 'Reset Password' button, the 'Password' input field, the 'Confirm Password' input field, and the 'Update' button.

Click Reset Password button

Input Password

Input the same Password

Click Update button

Logout

The image shows a user profile page for 'Admin' on the 'FASHIONone' platform. The page includes a sidebar with navigation options, a profile summary, and a settings form. A red box highlights the 'Logout' option in the top right user menu, with an orange callout box pointing to it that says 'Click Logout menu item'.

Navigation Menu:

- Home
- Users
- Clips
- Playlist
- Category
- Language
- PG Ratings
- SRT
- Servers
- Advertisement
- Filler

Profile Summary:

- Name:** Admin
- Role:** Administrator
- Clips Added:** 41,601
- Categories Added:** 0
- Servers Added:** 2

Settings Form:

- Settings:** Reset Password
- Name:** Admin
- Email:** admin@gmail.com
- Update:** [Red Button]

User Menu (Top Right):

- Admin
- Profile
- Logout** (highlighted in red)

Module / Feature

Application module focus on generating a fashion show video clips playlist

The screenshot shows the 'Clips' management interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: Home, Users, Clips (selected), Playlist, Category, Language, PG Ratings, SRT, Music, Servers, Advertisement, and Filter. The main content area has a header 'Add Clips' and a form with the following fields: Category (After Midnight), PG Ratings (Sexy), Date Added (04-26-2019 to 04-27-2019), SRT (Scooby Do), and Server (China). A 'Search' button is located below the form. Below the form is a table titled 'Clips' with the following data:

Clip ID	Title	Duration	Date Added	Added By	Action
1	earum	00:01:25	2019-04-26 08:46:21	Jomar Edano	
3	vel	00:01:12	2019-04-26 08:46:21	Jomar Edano	
4	ipsam	00:01:49	2019-04-26 08:46:21	Jomar Edano	
9	praesentium	00:01:28	2019-04-26 08:46:21	Jomar Edano	
10	delectus	00:01:53	2019-04-26 08:46:21	Jomar Edano	
16	debits	00:01:39	2019-04-26 08:46:21	Jomar Edano	
21	non	00:01:40	2019-04-26 08:46:22	Jomar Edano	
24	et	00:01:43	2019-04-26 08:46:22	Jomar Edano	
29	dolores	00:01:47	2019-04-26 08:46:22	Jomar Edano	

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the system clock as 2:23 PM on 4/27/2019.

The screenshot shows the 'Select Scheduling Process' dialog box. It has two buttons: 'Manual' and 'Input Excel File'. An 'Input Time' sub-dialog box is open, containing a warning message: 'This field use 24 hour format'. Below the warning are two time selection fields: 'Start Time' (00 : 00) and 'End Time' (23 : 45). 'Cancel' and 'Submit' buttons are at the bottom right of the sub-dialog. The background shows the application interface with the 'Playlist' menu item selected in the sidebar.

N.0 Messages

User email field got res and had “x” button on the upper left side. Still missing a message for user to know that the username or password inputted is not correct.

```
Illuminate\Database\QueryException (1045)
SQLSTATE[HY000] [1045] Access denied for user 'homestead@localhost' (using password: YES) (SQL: select *
from 'users' where 'email' = razz@gmail.com limit 1)

Previous exceptions
• SQLSTATE[HY000] [1045] Access denied for user 'homestead@localhost' (using password: YES) (1045)

Application frames (0)
All Frames (82)

Illuminate\Database\QueryException
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connection.php:664

Doctrine\DBAL\Driver\PDOException
Vendor:doctrine/dbal/Doctrine\DBAL/Driver/PDOConnection.php:31

PDOException
Vendor:doctrine/dbal/Doctrine\DBAL/Driver/PDOConnection.php:27

PDO_construct
Vendor:doctrine/dbal/Doctrine\DBAL/Driver/PDOConnection.php:27

Doctrine\DBAL\Driver\PDOConnection_construct
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connectors/Connector.php:67

Illuminate\Database/Connectors/Connector createPdoConnection
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connectors/Connector.php:46

Illuminate\Database/Connectors/Connector createConnection
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connectors/MySqlConnector.php:24

Illuminate\Database/Connectors/MySqlConnector connect
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connectors/ConnectionFactory.php:183

Illuminate\Database/Connectors/ConnectionFactory Illuminate\Database/Connectors(closure)
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connection.php:918

call_user_func
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connection.php:918

Illuminate\Database/Connection getPdo
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connection.php:943

Illuminate\Database/Connection getReadPdo
Vendor:laravel/framework/src/Illuminate/Database/Connection.php:999
```

```
1. *SQLSTATE[HY000] [1045] Access denied for user
```

```
Environment & details:
GET Data empty
POST Data
email "razz@gmail.com"
password "1234"
Files empty
Cookies
XSEF_TOKEN laravel_session
Session empty
Server/Request Data
DOCUMENT_ROOT "C:\Users\3oj14P\ahang\Documents\RazzDoc\2019-01-11\Play\list\play\list\ipb11c"
REMOTE_ADDR "127.0.0.1"
REMOTE_PORT "61812"
SERVER_SOFTWARE "PHP 7.3.2 Development Server"
SERVER_PROTOCOL "HTTP/1.1"
SERVER_NAME "127.0.0.1"
SERVER_PORT "8080"
REQUEST_URI "/login"
```

Service	Module	PID(s)	Port(s)	Actions
Apache	80/443	80, 443	80, 443	Stop Admin Config Logs Shell
MySQL	3306	3306	3306	Stop Admin Config Logs Explorer
FileZilla				Start Admin Config Logs Services
Mercurry				Start Admin Config Logs Help
Tomcat				Start Admin Config Logs Quit

```
01:43:17 PM [main] All prerequisites found
01:43:17 PM [main] Initializing Modules
01:43:17 PM [main] Starting Check-Timer
01:43:17 PM [main] Control Panel Ready
01:43:19 PM [Apache] Attempting to start Apache app.
01:43:19 PM [Apache] Status change detected: running
01:43:19 PM [mysql] Attempting to start MySQL app.
01:43:19 PM [mysql] Status change detected: running
```

Error message when User or Database name is not set in the .env database.

Styling error in the css file. No error because it did not affect in the app functionalities.

Message "Page controllers does not exist" and actions taken is to create PageControllers to solve the error of the app.

CITATION

Inoc, M. R. [Razel], Rosel, R. R. [Racquel], Edaño, J. E. [Jomar], & Cole, K. C. [Khim].
(2019). *AUTOMATION OF FASHION SHOW VIDEO PLAYLIST FOR FASHION ONE
INC.* [Thesis, University of San Carlos - Cebu, Talamban Campus].

 [Automation_of_Fashion_Show_Video_Playlist_2019.pdf](#)